

Catalog of Quality Problems in Data and Data Models

Structured set of quality problems for the identification of quality problems and requirements specification for quality analysis of datasets and data models for objects of the material culture

Developed as part of the BMBF-funded project KONDA

KONDA - Continuous quality management of dynamic research data on objects of material culture using the LIDO standard

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Date	2023-03-28
Version	2.0
Status	published
Release	2023-03

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1. Introduction

This catalog describes quality problems in research data focusing on material cultural objects and related data models. It has been compiled as part of the KONDA research project. This catalog aims to elicit requirements for a generic quality management process for research data through exchange with the community. The catalog is the result of qualitative interviews and a workshop with cultural heritage data experts. Within the catalog, each quality problem is described by a structured profile that includes aspects such as the quality dimensions affected, examples, causes, and ideas for improvement.

1.1. KONDA Project Description and Affiliates

KONDA is an interdisciplinary joint research project at the Universities of Göttingen and Marburg, Germany, funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) for three years, from 2019 to 2022. The acronym "KONDA" stands for continuous quality management of dynamic research data on material culture objects using the LIDO standard.

The aim of the project is to develop a systematic quality assurance for structured research data on objects of material culture, a desideratum for research in the humanities and cultural studies. The approach of a continuous quality management process (QM process), differentiated by data and data models over the entire data life cycle, is groundbreaking and pioneering. The participants of KONDA will develop a generic QM process for dynamic and partly uncertain research data. This process will be applied to the internationally accepted harvesting format Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO) for material culture objects. It will then be translated into specified curatorial criteria for data generation and curation of art historical research data describing different genres of material objects collected, for example, in museums and university collections.

The QM process is to be tested on selected databases, such as those of the Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte – Bildarchiv Foto Marburg and the University Collections of the University of Göttingen. The resulting QM processes will be documented in manuals and made available to the specialist public.

Affiliates

- Philipps-Universität Marburg / Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte – Bildarchiv Foto Marburg (DDK)¹
- Göttingen State and University Library²
- Philipps-Universität Marburg / Department of Mathematics and Computer Science³

1.2. Approach

The KONDA project aims to develop a quality management process for research data, especially for data on material cultural objects. This process must be oriented towards specific requirements. Experience has shown that the likelihood of changes being accepted by a group of people increases if

¹ <https://www.uni-marburg.de/de/fotomarburg>

² <https://www.sub.uni-goettingen.de/>

³ https://www.uni-marburg.de/fb12/en/index_html?set_language=en

these changes meet their interests. KONDA has therefore chosen to gather requirements for the quality of cultural heritage data in a *bottom-up* process.

Although KONDA is a project based in Germany, the results obtained during the project may also be of interest to an international audience.

During our work with the quality problems collected from different sources, we agreed to list problems instead of requirements, as we thought this might be more useful for our future work in the project context: Quality problems are something we can concretely observe in the data, whereas requirements are a more abstract concept. As our work is based on datasets from two institutions, it is likely that problems will become apparent, for example, during the instantiation of the quality management process to be developed. Structuring our findings in terms of problems rather than requirements simplifies this instantiation process, as we do not have to work *ex negativo*, by inferring which requirement is violated from a given problem. The document can therefore be read as a requirements specification, since we have defined a target state for the problem description.

In addition, by providing a catalog of quality problems that occur in data or data models, we aim to develop approaches to identify specific problems and can provide advice on how to solve a problem so that this deliverable can be published (with minor modifications) for external use.

To gather the requirements that serve as a basis for our work, we used three different methodological approaches:

- We held a **workshop** with 19 participants from different galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM institutions) within the wider cultural heritage community. Following Fouché et al.⁴, the community workshop was designed exploratively as a World Café (a qualitative social research tool) with facilitated sessions on six different topics, open-ended questions, discussions, and an evaluation based on the anonymous transcripts and flipcharts of the sessions. The questions were formulated in an open way to encourage the participants to discuss freely. The aim was to identify and discuss quality problems and solutions related to the topic. The results were recorded and analyzed by the project members. We did not record links between quality problems and individuals for privacy reasons.
- We conducted six semi-structured expert **interviews** with different domain experts involved in data acquisition, modeling, management, and use of research data, especially cultural heritage objects. We asked them about their opinions and experiences with data quality in the cultural heritage sector. The expert interviews were conducted following Bogner et al.⁵ from qualitative social research, with adapted guidelines such as questionnaires, pseudonymous digital recording, transcription, and analysis. We designed a questionnaire for each stakeholder group to guide the interviews. The interviews were conducted openly and the questions were used only as a guide. The overall aim of all questions was to identify and discuss quality problems. For each group, a list of well-known experts from the community was compiled, prioritized, and individuals were contacted. Prioritization was done with the help of people from the community and finally, the project members made the selection. The experts were assured of complete anonymity. This means that the names are only known within the project and the quality problems should not be attributed to individuals. All interviews were recorded and transcribed internally by the project members. Neither the audio files nor the transcriptions will be published for privacy reasons. The most important

⁴ Christa Fouché and Glenda Light. 2011. An Invitation to Dialogue: 'The World Café' In Social Work Research. Qualitative Social Work 10, 1 (March 2011), 28–48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1473325010376016>

⁵ Alexander Bogner, Beate Littig, and Wolfgang Menz. 2014. Interviews mit Experten. Eine praxisorientierte Einführung.

step was the analysis of the transcriptions from which the quality problems in this document were extracted.

- For all the problems collected in the catalog, we tried to find meaningful examples in two large databases of cultural heritage data. When the databases did not contain examples or the examples were not intuitively understandable, we presented fictitious examples. All empirical problems were validated by testing them in two datasets and their data models. These datasets came from the Center for Collection Development at the University of Göttingen⁶ and the Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte - Bildarchiv Foto Marburg⁷. These semi-structured research datasets comprised almost 30000 data records from the Center for Collection Development and over 1260000 from the Department of German Studies and Arts. The records represent cultural heritage objects, persons, and places, collected in various scientific disciplines such as ethnology, archaeology, history, biology, physics, and mathematics. As a result, the data describe a wide range of material objects, from prints to medical instruments. After recording the quality problems, we tested whether the quality problems occurred in the dataset to verify the existence and significance of the problem. For this purpose, we performed a partially manual and pattern-based sampling using XQuery and XSLT.

Along with these approaches, we have also reviewed the current research on quality problems in data models and the data itself.

1.3. Underlying Data and Data Models

For each quality problem profile, concrete examples are provided, preferably in the LIDO⁸ format. LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects), a specific CIDOC-CRM⁹ application, is an event-based XML format for describing museum or collection objects. Memory institutions use LIDO for "exposing, sharing and connecting data on the web"¹⁰. It can be applied to all cultural heritage disciplines, such as art, natural history, and technology.

For online publication on the website "Bildindex", which serves as a database for images and information on cultural heritage objects, the internal data is converted into LIDO-XML. The Bildindex also provides data from other institutions. Therefore, the LIDO dataset provided by Foto Marburg includes transformed LIDO data and LIDO data from other archives, museums, and libraries.¹¹

Furthermore, we included a dataset provided by the Center for Collection Development at the University of Göttingen. This dataset represents cultural heritage objects collected within the scope of various scientific disciplines such as ethnology, archaeology, history, biology, physics, or

⁶ Centre for Collection Development of Göttingen University. <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/440706.html> (Accessed 2020-08-05)

⁷ Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte - Bildarchiv Foto Marburg. <https://www.uni-marburg.de/de/fotomarburg> (Accessed 2020-08-05)

⁸ Erin Coburn, Richard Light, Gordon McKenna, Regine Stein, Axel Vitzthum. „LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects)". <http://network.icom.museum/cidoc/working-groups/lido/>. (Accessed 2020-08-04)

⁹ Martin Doerr, George Bruseker, Chryssoula Bekiari, Christian Emil Ore, Stephen Stead, Thanasis Velios. „CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM)". <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>. (Accessed 2020-08-04)

¹⁰ Erin Coburn, Richard Light, Gordon McKenna, Regine Stein, Axel Vitzthum. „LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects)". <http://network.icom.museum/cidoc/working-groups/lido/>. (Accessed 2020-08-04)

¹¹ Bildindex der Kunst und Architektur: <https://www.bildindex.de/cms/homepage/ueber-uns/partnerinstitutionen/archive-bibliotheken-verlage/> (Accessed 2020-08-05)

mathematics. The data thus describe a broad spectrum of material objects, from prints to medical instruments.

1.4. Structure of the Profiles for Quality Problems

The catalog describes 49 data quality problems and 16 data model quality problems. Other problems, such as those discussed in the interviews or during the community workshop, are out-of-scope.

In order to get a standardized overview of each data and data model quality problem, we decided to develop a profile that includes all dimensions that are of interest and are necessary for our further work. These include:

- A brief **description** that summarizes the problem
- The **main and other affected quality features** and an explanation of why these features are affected. These quality features have been defined within the project for data and data models. The features and their definitions are another deliverable of the project and will be published separately.
- A description of how the problem **affects data quality**. For quality problems that occur in data models there is an additional item describing how the problem **affects data model quality**.
- One or more **examples** to illustrate the problem. These examples were taken from real data (models) or constructed if the problem could not be found in our selected example datasets and data models or if there was no easily understandable example.
- A list of possible **causes** that have led to this quality problem
- The **stage of the research data cycle** in which the problem occurs or takes root. The stages are based on the RfII research data lifecycle¹².
- How this problem can be **identified** in a specific data record or database. This may include (semi-)automatic approaches as well as workflows.
- What a data record or database should look like when this problem has been solved (**target state**). **This part of the profile contains the actual requirements.**

1.5. Profile Template for Quality Problems

<ID> <Problem_Name>

Description: <What exactly is the problem?>

Mainly affected quality feature: <choose one of the categories below>

Other affected quality features:

<for data problems: syntactic accuracy, semantic accuracy, external accuracy, compliance, precision, internal completeness, external completeness, relevance, compactness, logical consistency, coherence, availability, confidentiality, integrity, data currency, data update currency, time concurrency, provenance, trustworthiness, temporal traceability, causal traceability, appropriateness, versatility>

<for model problems: syntactic accuracy, semantic accuracy, external accuracy, compliance, precision, internal completeness, external completeness, relevance, compactness, logical consistency, coherence, availability, confidentiality, integrity, data currency, data update currency, time concurrency, provenance,

¹² German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (RfII): The Data Quality Challenge. Recommendations for Sustainable Research in the Digital Turn, Göttingen 2020, 120 p. <http://www.rfii.de/?p=4203>. (Accessed 2020-08-05)

trustworthiness, temporal traceability, causal traceability, appropriateness, versatility>

Impact on data quality: <Why and how does the problem decrease data quality?>

Examples: <Data example: real or fictitious LIDO example, or abstract example>

Causes: <Why and under which circumstances does this problem occur? (e.g., model structure, system, practice, human error)>

Root in the data life cycle:

<plan, collect, assure, describe, submit, preserve, discover, integrate, analyze, publish>

Identification: <How can this problem be located in datasets? (e.g., pattern, metrics)>

Target state: <What should be achieved when fixing this problem?>

1.6. The Version of the catalog and future work

This is the second version of this catalog (2.0). As research within the KONDA project progresses, we want to keep the catalog open for changes and enrichments to its content. The iterative structure of the project allows us to collect additional requirements. We also want to be able to incorporate feedback from an international community. If you like to provide feedback or comments on this document, please contact konda@uni-marburg.de.

2. Quality Problems Concerning Data Models

This section encompasses all quality problems related to the design of the data model. According to the definition we developed at the beginning of the KONDA project, a data model is a model for the structured organization of the data of an application domain. It is a formalization of the set of entities to be described, their properties, and their relationships to other entities represented in the data. A distinction is usually made between conceptual, logical, and physical data models.^{13 14 15}

MODEL01 Incomplete data model

Description: Some information cannot be specified in the data model, generally due to missing fields.

This includes all problems that occur when the data model cannot capture the described objects with the required accuracy.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (missing necessary information of the domain of interest)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (missing the right elements to represent the domain of interest)
- external completeness (if the missing element should be a reference)

Impact on data model quality: The data model may be incomplete in both breadth and depth, which is why it may be inappropriate for some context of use in the domain of interest.

Impact on data quality: Although more knowledge about an object is available not all of it can be placed in the data because the respective fields are missing. This can even make the data useless to a user. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01](#), [DATA02.4](#), [DATA02.4.1](#), [DATA04.2](#), [DATA05](#), [DATA06.5](#), [DATA06.7](#), [DATA09](#)

Examples:

- It is not possible to model all necessary entities, e.g. both cultural heritage and scientific objects
- It is not possible to provide information obtained from oral statements (e.g. calls, talks, conversations, ...) as source
- A specific field is not defined as repeatable, but there are cases where multiple values should be assigned in a data record, e.g., actor in a model for paintings (fictional example)

```
<xs:element name="roleActor" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1" id="roleActor">
```

Instead of

```
<xs:element name="roleActor" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" id="roleActor">
```

Causes:

- The data model was developed without (proper) requirements engineering
- Requirements have changed over time
- No involvement of domain experts during the development of the data model

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

- Extensive use of free text fields
- Misuse of elements/statements (cf. [DATA02.4](#))

Target state: All required information related to an entity can be provided in specific data fields in a structured manner (i.e., without the use of free text).

¹³ Paulo Merson: Data Model as an Architectural View. 2009. Software Engineering Institute, Carnegie Mellon University, 10.1184/R1/6572864.v1 (Accessed 2020-08-04)

¹⁴ Elmasri, Navathe: Fundamentals of Database Systems, .3 edition, Verlag: Pearson Studium, ISBN: 978-0-136-08620-8, 2011

¹⁵ Saake, G., Sattler, K.-U., Heuer, A.: Datenbanken - Konzepte und Sprachen, 4. Edition. MITP. ISBN: 978-3-8266-9057-0, 2010

MODEL01.1 No value exclusions ("not B")

Description: For some data models it is not possible to mark explicit exclusions of values.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (not detailed enough for the purpose of modeling)

Other affected quality features: semantic accuracy (missing the right elements to represent the domain of interest)

Impact on data model quality: The data model can only capture positive values, so it may be incomplete in depth. Thus, fewer possibilities are given, which may be essential for some context of use.

Impact on data quality: In some cases, we can restrict a set of possible values by excluding certain elements. When a data model does not allow to express the exclusion of certain values, another form of modeling, "possibly X, Y, Z but not A" has to be provided. If this is not the case, knowledge in the form of "A is not the case" is lost, resulting in a loss of information. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.3.2](#), [DATA01.3.3](#), [DATA06](#), [DATA09](#)

Examples:

- No value exclusions available in the model to implement statements like "I do not know who created this, but it was certainly not artist X!".
- No exclusions available for lido:date elements:

```
<xs:complexType name="dateComplexType" id="dateComplexType">
  <xs:sequence>
    <xs:element name="earliestDate" minOccurs="0" id="earliestDate">
      ...
    </xs:element>
    <xs:element name="latestDate" minOccurs="0" id="latestDate">
      ...
    </xs:element>
  </xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
instead of
<xs:complexType name="dateComplexType" id="dateComplexType">
  <xs:sequence>
    <xs:element name="noteBeforeDate" minOccurs="0" id="beforeDate">
      ...
    </xs:element>
  </xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
```

Causes:

- The data model does not provide a way to express value-exclusions

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

- Since this information may be provided in a free text field: Query them for keywords (e.g. "not")
- If information is omitted these cases cannot be identified automatically but only with human intellect/expert knowledge of the catalogers

Target state: It should be possible to express knowledge of the form "possibly X, Y, Z but not A" or "not A" in the data when there is evidence that "A" is not the case.

MODEL02 Unspecific field concepts

Description: The description of individual fields of a data model is so unspecific that it leaves a lot of room for interpretation. Thus, different pieces of information may fit. Sometimes this is desirable, e.g., an optional comment field, but non-specific definitions increase the diversity of instances, which reduces comparability and can lead to misunderstandings.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (not being detailed enough)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (lack of precision leads to misunderstanding of objects or elements)
- semantic accuracy (lack of correct elements for each of the multiple information)

Impact on data model quality: While theoretically applicable to many contexts of use, the data model might not fit some contexts of use for precisely the generic reason. This type of accuracy is essential for a complete and accurate data model. Furthermore, unclear and unspecific descriptions and definitions reduce comprehensibility. This can lead to [MODEL11](#).

Impact on data quality: An unclear specification of the desired data leads to very heterogeneous data values regarding subject and precision. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.3.2](#), [DATA02.4](#), [DATA04.2](#), [DATA06](#)

Examples:

- A measurement value without specification of height, length, or weight
- A place could be general. The string value is too unspecific and does not specify if an address, geolocation, or what form of location is meant: (fictional example)

```
<xs:element name="place" type="lido:placeComplexType" minOccurs="0" id="place"
type="xs:string">
  <xs:annotation>
    <xs:documentation>
      <tei:ab type="description">Defines information about a place.</tei:ab>
      <tei:ab type="label">Place</tei:ab>
    </xs:documentation>
  </xs:annotation>
</xs:element>
```

Causes:

- Unclear field concept in the data model

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

- Confusion and insecurities: Catalogers not sure what to
- Heterogeneous data

Target state: All fields/elements/statements in the data model are clearly defined.

MODEL03 Use of free-text fields instead of LOD references

Description: The information is provided in free-text fields (and therefore manually entered). The concept of a field in the data model is not specific enough. Instead of a reference to a Linked Open Data object or authority file, it is impossible to identify the information provided with a LOD-Reference.¹⁶ Therefore, the description or term cannot be identified by a machine.

Mainly affected quality feature: external completeness (missing link types and insufficient detail)

Other affected quality features:

- internal completeness (if the information is not detailed enough due to missing references and information, internal completeness is violated)
- external accuracy (not the right elements and correct relationships between them)
- compliance (failure to implement linked data references where applicable violates conventions)

Impact on data model quality: Using free text fields instead of LOD references massively reduces the possibility of linking within the data model and across data models. Thus, the data model is less complete and accurate for different contexts of use. In addition, linking is required in different guidelines so that conventions may be violated depending on the domain of interest.

Impact on data quality: If information, e.g., about a person, is provided manually instead of relying on LOD/authority files, the way information about that person is provided may be heterogeneous if catalogers use different phrases or styles of description (cf. [DATA01.3.4](#)).

Manual editorial corrections are required to avoid this. In addition, when using LOD/authority files, changes to information about a person, for example, must be added manually, which may result in an automatic update when the new information is added to the authority file system. Also, providing information in free text fields is an unstructured way of distributing information, making it difficult to reuse the data. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.3](#), [DATA02.3](#), [DATA04.2](#), [DATA05](#), [DATA10](#)

Examples:

- The element is defined as a string value to specify the term, rather than defining elements as references to a vocabulary entry:

```
<lido:objectWorkType>
  <lido:term>Kupferstich</lido:term>
</lido:objectWorkType>
instead of
<lido:objectWorkType>
  <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300041341">
    <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">copper engravings (visual works)</skos:prefLabel>
    <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Kupferstich (Druckgrafik)</skos:prefLabel>
  </skos:Concept>
</lido:objectWorkType>
```

Causes:

- Using LOD/authority files is not possible due to the data model (e.g., no URIs¹⁷ allowed)
- Using LOD/authority files is not implemented in the cataloging software
- Lack of knowledge: LOD/authority files generally unknown; what vocabulary is appropriate for what use case?

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

- Check if a URI is provided (REGEX)¹⁸

¹⁶ LOD = Linked Open Data: <https://www.w3.org/wiki/LinkedData>. (Accessed 2020-08-24)

¹⁷ URI = Uniform Resource Identifier: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uniform_Resource_Identifier. (Accessed 2020-08-24)

¹⁸ REGEX = Regular Expression: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regular_expression. (Accessed 2020-08-24)

Target state: All information in a record should be linked to LOD objects/authority files where possible.

MODEL04 Structural redundancy in data models

Description: There can be several model elements with the same meaning. A data model allows the same subject matter to be encoded in multiple ways.

Mainly affected quality feature: compactness (model contains redundant model elements)

Other affected quality features:

- coherence (violation of the coherence of the data model in itself)
- appropriateness (multiple elements with the same meaning lead to misunderstandings)

Impact on data model quality: The data model contains some accidental complexity.. This makes it less compact and understandable, making it more challenging to use, such as transformations, tests, and documentation.

Impact on data quality: By encoding the same fact or phenomenon in different ways a dataset becomes heterogeneous and less accurate. An application using the data must consider all possible options. If there are different elements or relationships, this can lead to overhead in the application and elements/relationships may be overlooked. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.3](#), [DATA03.1](#), [DATA03.2](#), [DATA06.8](#)

Examples:

- A schema allows for `tei:name` and `tei:persName` to coexist, both being used to encode the name of a person¹⁹
- Events can be structurally modeled in different ways. For example, in LIDO, events are essential and modeled in depth. This means that information can be moderated both as an event and in other ways. A birth date can be associated with a person and at the same time as an event birth.

Causes:

- Human error during data model creation: Missed ambiguous elements/relationships
- The data model describes the complex and/or diverse entities and must be flexible
- The structure of the data model is not specified

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

- Elements/predicates/fields with similar meaning
- Different substructures of the same element

Target state: The data model should be flexible enough to encode everything that needs to be encoded, without allowing for heterogeneous data or inaccuracies. In most cases, the model designer must make a trade-off between model flexibility and heterogeneity.

¹⁹ TEI: Text Encoding Initiative <https://tei-c.org/>. (Accessed 2020-08-24)

MODEL05 Changes to the data model structure

Description: During the lifetime of a data model, its structure can change. In this process, individual fields can be added, deleted, redefined, or moved to other locations in the structure. The previous versions of the data model are not available (anymore) as (version) history and individual changes are not causally traceable.

Mainly affected quality feature: temporal traceability (continuous change and improvement of the data model)

Other affected quality features: causal traceability (if the reasons for the changes are not obvious)

Impact on data model quality: Even though continuous changes are positive in many respects, it is essential for many users and processes that the changes are transparent and traceable. If not, the use of newer versions can be discouraged. This may concern, e.g., transformations.

Impact on data quality: As the data model evolves, an institution must ensure that older data records still conform to the new data model; otherwise, older data records will be unusable or may become incorrect when elements are redefined. A new data model can also reduce the reusability of the data if third-party software still uses an older version of the data model. Therefore, it is necessary to document the used data model version used in the data ([DATA07.2](#)). The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.1](#), [DATA01.3](#), [DATA02.4](#), [DATA03](#), [DATA05](#), [DATA06](#), [DATA07](#), [DATA10.2](#)

Examples:

- LIDO1.0 and LIDO1.1 are both available in git. However, they are independent files. Thus, a comparison and traceability between these versions are not available.

Causes:

- Changing requirements
- Problems in data modeling that require changes
- New technical capabilities

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification: Structurally heterogeneous data

Target state: Data should be structurally homogeneous and conform to the latest version of the data model.

MODEL06 Incomprehensible (complex) model

Description: If the data model is used to describe many different phenomena in great detail, the model will be very large and also complex. The more complex and multi-faceted a data model is, the more difficult it is to understand.

Mainly affected quality feature: appropriateness (complexity and information structures with a high level of detail reduce understandability)

Other affected quality features:

- compactness (risk of unnecessary information concerning complexity is high)
- relevance (if unnecessary elements, properties, or link types are defined)

Impact on data model quality: Very detailed structures reduce comprehensibility and significantly increase the effort for writing transformations and documentation. This could lead to [MODEL09](#).

Impact on data quality:

- If the person editing a data record does not fully understand the data model, the data s/he creates may be of poor quality by misusing the model. Thus, information is expressed in inappropriate constructs or the wrong fields.
- In addition, the high complexity of a data model can affect the time required to create, edit, or even read a data record.
- Complex and multifaceted data models make it difficult to exchange data and map it to other models.
- The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA02.3](#), [DATA02.4](#), [DATA10.1](#), [DATA10.3](#), [DATA12](#)

Examples:

- Data models with element types of which only a certain number are used in the database.
- Data models implemented using numbered element names could have the same description, but use different numbers, depending on where in the document structure it appears. The model would be easier to understand if the same element names were used where the same type of information is expected.
- <partOfPlace> in LIDO is a recursive element that is used for structured information about a place but the structure is not specified, just as there is no information about whether or not to use the state as an element:

```
<xs:complexType name="placeComplexType" id="placeComplexType">
  ...
  <xs:element name="partOfPlace" type="lido:placeComplexType" minOccurs="0"
    maxOccurs="unbounded" id="partOfPlace">...</xs:element>
  ...
</xs:complexType>
```

Causes:

- Model is intended to be used to describe many different types of entities or phenomena in great detail
- Model grows over time

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification: (see Genero et al. 2005, Arendt Diss 2014 on class model metrics)

- Number of entities
- Number of relations (per entity)
- Number of attributes (per entity)
- Depths of hierarchy

Target state: The data model should be no more complex than necessary to describe the entities of interest. Users with little experience in data modeling and little knowledge of the domain of interest should be able to understand and use the model after a brief introduction and training period.

MODEL07 Model with inaccurate statements about the domain of interest

Description: The model does not semantically match the domain of interest. The model structure (or ordering of data fields) implies dependencies and relationships that do not match the domain of interest. For example, in XML, the model hierarchy is poorly ordered when more general or independent fields are represented as more specific or dependent fields. This structure, therefore, implies the wrong relationships between fields.

Mainly affected quality feature: semantic accuracy (violation of the correct elements and relationships between them)

Other affected quality features:

- coherence (mismatched relationships that affect consistency with other data models)
- compliance (model structure may not comply with standards/regulations of the domain of interest)
- appropriateness (non-compliant relationships lead to misunderstandings)

Impact on data model quality: Inaccurate statements about the domain of interest reduce the usability of the data model in these domains. Further, inaccurate statements can lead to inconsistencies in other data models, violate policies, and affect the understandability of the data model.

Impact on data quality: Values are not well-placed, making data presentation and overview difficult when using the data. The following data problem may (also) result: [DATA02.4](#)

Examples:

- Wrong relation direction: The owner of the object is Saarlandmuseum, but the object can't be the owner of Saarlandmuseum.
- In XML bad hierarchy: No nesting of dependent values

```
<object>
  <title>Gemüesestilleben</title>
  <name>Max Slevogt</name>
  <person>
    <GND-ID>http://d-nb.info/gnd/118614940</GND-ID>
  </person>
</object>
instead of:
<object>
  <title>Gemüesestilleben</title>
  <person>
    <name>Max Slevogt</name>
    <GND-ID>http://d-nb.info/gnd/118614940</GND-ID>
  </person>
</object>
```

Causes:

- Bad design
- No consultation of experts during and after the modeling process

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification: Manual

Target state: All dependencies and relations of values are represented in the model structure

MODEL08 Too few mandatory fields

Description: There are too few mandatory fields in the data model to get a true sense of the object if all optional fields are left empty.

Mainly affected quality feature: semantic accuracy (too few mandatory fields can lead to incorrect information as a whole and incorrect relationships between elements)

Other affected quality features:

Impact on data model quality: Although fewer mandatory fields make the data model theoretically feasible for multiple domains of interest, it may reduce accuracy in those domains, a common requirement in many contexts of use to create accurate data.

Impact on data quality: Although a data record exists for an object, the record is not usable for anything other than stating that the object exists. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01](#), [DATA04.2](#), [DATA06.7](#), [DATA10.2](#)

Examples:

- In LIDO only the object type, the object's title, the record ID, the record type, and the record source are mandatory elements. Even though LIDO was designed as an exchange format, it is also used as an acquisition format. So there are two different contexts of use.
 - For the acquisition, it may lead to missing, incomplete, and inaccurate data.
 - For exchange, it can lead to institutions exporting to LIDO but not exporting important information because it is optional. This may also lead to missing, incomplete, and inaccurate data.

Causes: Design of the data model

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

- Assessing the data model for flags or cardinality that imply mandatory fields

Target state: There are enough mandatory fields to provide a thorough impression of an object described in the record. Useful fields may vary for different institutions or object types.

MODEL09 Missing documentation in the data model

Description: The data model is not properly documented. This includes a complete lack of documentation as well as partly missing documentation.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (documentation is an essential guideline of each description language / modeling language)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (missing information about model elements reduces the understandability of the model)

Impact on data model quality: Documentation is an essential part of the data model. Lack of documentation can lead to unacceptability, problems with instantiation, and the creation of transformations.

Impact on data quality: A data model that is not properly documented hinders its use at all levels, as element definitions may be unclear (leading to problems in the implementation in acquisition software), decisions for a particular design may be obscure (making it less extensible), and it is less reusable due to possible reduced understandability. Furthermore, the data model could be misused for other purposes or scopes. For example, a data model class could be used for a different entity. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA02.3](#), [DATA02.4](#), [DATA04.2](#), [DATA06.8](#), [DATA10](#)

Examples:

- An XSD without xs:documentation

Causes:

- Lack of resources or time during the data model design
- Model designer regards the model as self-explanatory
- Designer not familiar with best practices

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification: No documentation (either as a separate file/website or as documentation elements/strings) is available in the data model.

Target state: A data model should provide documentation about itself.

MODEL10 Lack of unique identifiers

Description: A data record lacks a unique identifier to distinguish it from other records.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (unique identifiers are relevant details of the domain of interest)

Other affected quality features:

- external completeness (unique identifiers could be a requirement for external identification)
- coherence (the risk of elements with the same meaning is increased)
- compliance (If the identifiers are not required by the data model but by guidelines)

Impact on data model quality: Data models cannot meet the requirements of many contexts of use. Unique identifiers are often must-haves for completeness and are specified in guidelines.

Impact on data quality:

- Data records are not identifiable.
- The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA05](#)

Examples:

- Missing a unique identifier like the identifier element in LIDO: <lido:recordID/>

Causes:

- The data model does not provide field/element/statement
- IDs are not automatically generated and forgotten during data acquisition

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification: Records lack unique values that distinguish them from other records.

Target state: All records should be identified by a specific value that serves as an identifier.

MODEL11 Multiple units of information encoded together in a single field

Description: The data model requires that several different kinds of information about the described entity are encoded together in a single field. They are separated by, e.g., commas or spaces.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (an element property should contain only one unit of information)

Other affected quality features:

- internal completeness (data model lacks detailed modeling information)
- appropriateness (multiple kinds of information reduce understandability)
- coherence (different kinds of information lead to heterogeneity)

Impact on data model quality: These data models may in conflict with some guidelines given for the domains of interest. There is a lack of accuracy in depth, which is often a requirement of various contexts of use.

Impact on data quality: Values are less machine-readable. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA02.4](#), [DATA11](#)

Examples:

- A data model that combines height, width, length, or weight into one unit of measurement
- The display element in LIDO, e.g., for measurements, is used to display human-understandable information on a website, and in practice results in multiple information being encoded in one element.

```
<lido:displayObjectMeasurements>203 x 314 cm</lido:displayObjectMeasurements>
```

Causes:

- Simple models with a small number of fields
- The data model does not provide multiple fields for this information

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification:

- The data model documentation lists multiple information aspects that should be encoded in the field
- Regex: Detect the use of delimiters or long entries

Target state: Different kinds of information should be represented in multiple different fields.

MODEL12 Inappropriate primitive data types

Description: The data model does not specify appropriate primitive data types for corresponding fields. The values that can be entered in a particular field are not appropriately restricted. Often, many fields of type string are specified, even though they represent numeric or temporal information.

Mainly affected quality feature: semantic accuracy (Required information that is not correctly modeled affects correctness)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (non-precise information model leads to misunderstandings about what information is meant)
- internal completeness (the model fails to cover information that is detailed enough to be complete)
- coherence (the model fails to cover information in detail that is common in the domain, e.g., in other data models)
- compliance (the model fails to capture constraints that are part of the rules or conventions of the domain of interest)

Impact on data model quality: First and foremost, the accuracy of the individual elements is concerned. Element definition, documentation, and constraints should be coherent. Otherwise, usability is highly restricted.

Impact on data quality: Data quality is decreased when the type of the expected information is not precisely specified, as this allows unwanted (i.e., unexpected and invalid) values to be entered in this field. This prevents the direct comparison of values entered in this field across records. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA1.3](#), [DATA02.4](#), [DATA04](#), [DATA09](#), [DATA11](#), [DATA12](#)

Examples:

- Data models in which each primitive element is of type string
- The date in LIDO, e.g., in lido:earliestDate, allows string values instead of specific date formats

```
<xs:element name="earliestDate" minOccurs="0" id="earliestDate">
...
<xs:extension base="xs:string">
```

Causes:

- Data model designers want to allow the flexible, implicit encoding of additional information in the same field, rather than modeling this additional information explicitly

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

Target state: By specifying an appropriate primitive data type the accepted values for a field should be limited as much as possible. Each field should represent exactly one aspect of information.

MODEL13 Vocabularies and thesauri

MODEL13.1 Unattended vocabularies or thesauri

Description: It is necessary to maintain vocabularies and thesauri. This includes correcting, updating, and completing the associated databases. There should also be a firm concept of what the vocabulary is about.

Mainly affected quality feature: semantic accuracy (outdated vocabulary entries lead to outdated data)

Other affected quality features:

- compliance (communities demand that vocabularies are kept up to date and constantly maintained)
- external completeness (unattended vocabulary data can lead to missing properties of the vocabulary itself)
- internal completeness (if the vocabulary is for internal use)
- coherence (partially unattended vocabulary data can lead to consistency problems such as duplicates or data with multiple meanings)
- appropriateness (lack of maintenance of vocabulary concept and structure can lead to misunderstandings)
- data currency (as vocabulary entries become outdated)
- time concurrency (when some entries are updated and others are still outdated)

Impact on data model quality: Unattended vocabularies reduce their usability in other data models. It is essential to maintain vocabularies that are already in use. Poor quality of vocabulary already in use has far-reaching effects on linked data models and their instantiated data.

Impact on data quality:

- Missing links between data values
- Synonymous data cannot be identified
- Links to wrong terms reduce quality
- Retrieval becomes worse (recall and precision)
- The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.1.1](#), [DATA01.1.2](#), [DATA01.1.3](#), [DATA01.1.5](#), [DATA10](#)

Examples:

- "church" does not contain a reference to "building"
- "mug" is not entered as a synonym for "cup"
- "chappel" is missing in the vocabulary, but used in the data
- A copper engraving (Kupferstich) should be described by the term (Sachbegriff) „5230: Druck" plus the naming of „5300: Kupferstich" as technique. „Kupferstich (Druck)" has been added as an entry in vocabulary 5230, also, "Kupferstich (Technik)" can be found in subject area 5300 for techniques. So there are two existing ways to express the same information.

Causes:

- No active tending of the vocabulary
- No automatic alert when entering values
- Concept of the vocabulary changes / gets fuzzy over time
- Several institutions sharing a single vocabulary

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, Collect, Assure, Analyze

Identification:

- Terms used in a record's field/element/statement not present in the defined vocabulary
- Vocabulary contains gaps

Target state:

- Vocabularies are up-to-date and maintained

- All used values are fully specified (definition, preferred/alternative, narrower/broader term, ...)
- All data fields of the vocabulary are specified
- Synonyms are marked as such, i.e., as an alternative term

MODEL13.2 Inaccurate controlled vocabulary

Description: The controlled vocabulary does not meet the context-specific accuracy requirements.

This occurs when the controlled vocabulary is referenced by other data that needs to be more accurate. Temporal and spatial data are often affected.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (communities require vocabularies to be accurate and specific)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (violated if the community believes the vocabulary is inaccurate)
- internal completeness (imprecise can lead to missing properties of the vocabulary itself)
- external completeness (if the vocabulary is public)
- coherence (partly inaccurate vocabulary data can lead to consistency problems)

Impact on data model quality: Inaccurate vocabularies violate guidelines on accuracy, completeness, and coherence. In particular, this quality affects linked data models and staged data.

Impact on data quality:

- Imprecision within a controlled vocabulary leads either to unwanted imprecision in other data that reference the controlled vocabulary ([DATA06.2](#)) or to the omission of references to controlled vocabulary ([DATA10.2](#)). The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.1.1](#), [DATA01.1.2](#), [DATA01.1.3](#), [DATA01.1.5](#), [DATA10](#)

Examples:

- Authority data only provides information about large cities (e.g., Mannheim), but not about suburbs.
- Controlled vocabulary provides information for the material "paper", but does not allow to differentiate in detail, e.g., between "transparent paper" and "tracing paper".

Causes:

- A controlled vocabulary is referenced in use cases other than those for which it was designed and intended for. More appropriate authority data is missing.
- As with values from continuous domains, the level of granularity can theoretically be refined indefinitely. A controlled vocabulary can never be precise enough for all possible use cases.

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, Collect, Integrate

Identification:

- Locate inaccurate data and manually verify that it is caused by an imprecise controlled vocabulary
- Missing references to a controlled vocabulary

Target state: A controlled vocabulary should meet the context-specific requirements concerning precision.

MODEL13.3 Incomplete controlled vocabulary

Description: The controlled vocabulary is too restricted. As a result, it is incomplete in terms of the concepts needed to describe the phenomena at hand.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (missing terms that are key concepts of the community using the vocabulary affect internal completeness)

Other affected quality features:

- external completeness (missing terms in detail, e.g., properties that are relevant to the community that should use the vocabulary, affect community-wide completeness, thus external completeness)

Impact on data model quality: Completeness of vocabularies is essential for data models in domains of interest and contexts of use. This has implications not only for the vocabulary itself but also for linked data models and instances of them in the form of data.

Impact on data quality: If the controlled vocabulary does not contain a term to make a correct statement about the entity of interest, we can either not make a statement at all or give an inappropriate term and thus make an incorrect statement. Thus, data quality is reduced because the data does not describe the entity as correctly and closely as possible when the controlled vocabulary is expanded. The following data problems may (also) result: [DATA01.1.1](#), [DATA01.1.2](#), [DATA01.1.3](#), [DATA01.1.5](#), [DATA10](#)

Examples:

- The source of a statement can only be indicated by a reference to literature, but not, for example, by a historical photograph or the expertise of the cataloger

Causes:

- The controlled vocabulary grows over time, rather than being fully designed for all use cases prior to deployment.
- New use cases (e.g., new projects) emerge after the controlled vocabulary is created

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

- Controlled fields that are left blank

Target state: The controlled vocabulary should contain all terms necessary to make correct statements about the entity in all intended use cases.

3. Quality Problems Concerning Data

This section encompasses all quality problems connected to the data itself, i.e. the respective data record instances. As a data record, we define a certain amount (1-n) of data fields that are connected through their content describing one entity.

DATA01 Data Volume

Problems in the context of the quantity of data.

DATA01.1 Lack of data

DATA01.1.1 Lack of data - empty fields

Description: Fields in the data record are empty. This means that the expected information is not provided. Application profiles may be used to specify mandatory and optional fields.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (lack of expected values for attributes and elements)

Other affected quality features:

- compliance (if there is a corresponding specification for the data, standards, conventions, or regulations might be violated)
- syntactic accuracy (if there is a corresponding data model specification for the data fields exists, the syntactic specification might be violated)
- semantic accuracy (incompleteness violates correctly represented information of the domain of interest)

Impact on data quality: Empty fields reduce data quality because they imply that information about the described entity is missing from the record but do not further specify why it is missing (e.g. information is not known according to the current state of research vs. not enough time for research when creating the record).

Examples:

- lido:term is empty

```
<lido:subjectConcept>
  <lido:term/>
</lido:subjectConcept>
```

Causes:

- Human error and insecurities of catalogers
- Part of the information cannot be determined with up-to-date methods and by evaluating all available sources
- Part of the information is unknown to the person editing the data record – the resources may not be sufficient for overcoming gaps in knowledge through research
- Resources are not sufficient for transferring all known information to the data record
- Information is ignored as it is being misinterpreted, misjudged, differs from expectations or the person does not know how to handle it
- The person editing the data record does not understand the field's specification

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Empty strings
- Missing statements

Target state: The data should describe the entity of interest as completely as possible according to the current state of research. Mandatory fields should not be empty. In the case of empty fields, the reason for it to be empty should be specified ([DATA06.7](#)).

DATA01.1.2 Lack of data - incomplete fields

Description: Fields are only partially filled. Not all desired information is stated in the model. Fields can be incomplete due to a lack of knowledge (only partial information) or formal mistakes (lack of units). Hence there is only sometimes a possibility to complete those fields

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (expected values are incomplete for attributes and/or elements)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (incompleteness violates correctly represented information of the domain of interest)
- syntactic accuracy (if the corresponding specification for the data fields exists, the syntactic specification might be violated)
- precision (fields logically are, in most cases, not exactly as expected if the data field is partially filled)
- appropriateness (partly filled fields may affect the understandability of related elements)
- compliance (if the corresponding specification for the data fields exists, standards, conventions, or regulations will be violated)
- external completeness (if the information is intended to be given as a reference)

Impact on data quality: Information about the described entity is missing from the record.

Examples:

- Number without units:

```
<lido:resourceMeasurementsSet>  
  <lido:measurementUnit/>  
  <lido:measurementValue>350</lido:measurementValue>  
</lido:resourceMeasurementsSet>
```

- Date without month and day:

```
<lido:eventDate>  
  <lido:date>1907</lido:date>  
</lido:eventDate>
```

Causes:

- Lack of research knowledge
- Implicit encoding of uncertainty (e.g., imprecision)
- Human error: Work has been interrupted and not been completed

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Fields do not contain all the desired information.

Target state: All fields meet their requirements on information density.

DATA01.1.3 Lack of records

Description: Records that should be in the database are missing for various reasons.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (if the records belong to the dataset)

Other affected quality features:

- external accuracy (if links are available but not valid)
- external completeness (related entity instances are missing)

Impact on data quality:

- When a record is missing in the database, the dataset is not complete (though this might be a permanent state due to acquisition practices). Thus queries over the entire database might lead to erroneous results and it is hardly possible to defer statements like "in the collection X, Y is the case". Furthermore, missing data records might cause a loss of trustworthiness and reputation of an institution on the user side, e.g., when a user knows a specific drawing is held in the institution, but the data record needs to be included.
- Information about the related data record is missing. References cannot be resolved and are unclear, thus impeding further use of the still-existing record. ([DATA05.2](#))

Examples:

- A painting is displayed in a museum but is missing in its database.

Causes:

- Practice: Cataloguing can only start after acquiring an object. The needed time for data creation depends on the resources.
- Technical: Data loss, database index not updated/not working, wrong references, ...

Root in the data life cycle: Collect, publish

Identification: If there are references to an object that does not have a data record, this might be discovered by an unsuccessful resolving query. Otherwise, the lack of a data record is either known (or discovered by chance) or not.

Target state: Each object should have one data record.

DATA01.1.4 Lack of source

Description: In a data field, an interpretative (i.e., non-measurable) statement is made without providing a source (e.g., a signature, historical document, (scientific) paper, Wikipedia, the expertise of the cataloger) for it.

Mainly affected quality feature: provenance (lack of sources significantly affects the plausibility)

Other affected quality features:

- external accuracy (if the information is provided by a non-valid link)
- trustworthiness (interpretative statements without references generally affect trustworthiness)
- external completeness (missing sources to information based on external sources are incomplete information)
- coherence (interpretative information increases coherence)

Impact on data quality: For traceability and trustworthiness, it is necessary to specify the source of acquired and registered information.

Examples:

- "'The Man with the Golden Helmet' is no longer attributed to Rembrandt since 1985" without providing a source for this information
- "Some scholars state that XYZ" without providing a source for this information:

```
<lido:objectDescriptionWrap>
  <lido:objectDescriptionSet>
    <lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
      Das berühmte Bild, dessen Bedeutung noch umstritten ist, befand sich 1498
      in der Via Larga im Palast von [...]
    </lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
    <lido:sourceDescriptiveNote>
    </lido:sourceDescriptiveNote>
  </lido:objectDescriptionSet>
</lido:objectDescriptionWrap>
```

Causes:

- Sources are provided in a non-structured way, e.g., in a free text field
- Acquisition software does not provide an input field for sources
- The data model does not allow for giving sources
- A statement (though being interpretative) is widely accepted as *communis opinio* and thus no source is provided
- Providing sources is out of scope in an acquisition project

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- By validation, if providing sources is mandatory in the data model (low effort)
- Searching free text fields (high effort)

Target state:

- Providing sources for specific data fields or relations between entities should be possible. Preferably all statements should be verified by a source.

DATA01.1.5 Lack of information about the person responsible for uncertain statements

Description: If uncertain statements are not based on sound sources but rather a single person's subjective interpretation, the person (e.g., cataloger) who is responsible for making a said statement should be denoted in the data. Since this person then serves as the source for the statement, this is a special case of [DATA01.1.4](#).

Mainly affected quality feature: trustworthiness (uncertain statements directly affect believability)

Other affected quality features:

- external completeness (if the missing sources of information is based on external sources)
- internal completeness (if the missing sources of information are intended to be given within the dataset)

Impact on data quality: In case statements are uncertain, e.g., because the knowledge stated is inferred without documented evidence, it should be traceable who has decided to make this statement. Otherwise, the data might suggest uncertainty as to general "knowledge". Also, providing the person responsible leads to better transparency and therefore increases the trustworthiness of the data.

Examples:

- Assume it is highly probable that an object has been created at a certain location, but there is no definite evidence (e.g., evidence by documents). Nevertheless, the place of creation is stated in the data, but no clue has inferred said place.
- "Some scholars state that XYZ" without providing a source for this information:

```
<lido:objectDescriptionWrap>
  <lido:objectDescriptionSet>
    <lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
      Das berühmte Bild wurde 1677, vermutlich von Paulo Di Senti, gestohlen
      [...]
    </lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
    <lido:sourceDescriptiveNote>
    </lido:sourceDescriptiveNote>
  </lido:objectDescriptionSet>
```

Causes:

- The data model does not allow for providing authors (e.g., cataloger)
- The author statement was forgotten during the acquisition
- Author statements are out of the scope of the acquisition project

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification:

- Elements, attributes, or statements that describe uncertainty lack an additional element, attribute, or statement for the statement's author

Target state: All statements marked as uncertain should provide an author or source for the uncertain information.

DATA01.1.6 Lack of metadata

Description: Metadata about data records (e.g., which institution has created the data, licensing, identifier) are not specified in the data. More specifically, the following types of metadata may be of interest but still be missing from the data: Time spent for creating the record, level of expertise of the person editing the record, change history, provenance, context of creation: project, focus, goal/purpose, limitations, resources, quality dimensions considered, research question, obligatory fields ...

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (required metadata affects the completeness of data elements of the domain of interest)

Other affected quality features:

- causal traceability (information about the creation and modification of the record affects the traceability)
- temporal traceability (information about the creation and modification of the record affects the traceability)
- trustworthiness (if the missing information is intended to be given by a significant set of people)
- provenance (if the missing information is intended to be given by a source to a verifiable information)
- appropriateness (missing metadata basically affects understandability)
- external completeness (missing sources to information based on external sources, identifiers, and links to licenses or rights statements lead to incomplete information)

Impact on data quality: Data records that lack meta-information, e.g., about the data creator or license, are not trustworthy or re-usable since a user needs to comprehend the data origin and possible usage. This may even lead to the data record being completely useless. Missing metadata makes it harder to reconstruct how and why data quality problems have emerged. This complicates the quality improvement of old data.

Examples:

- missing published identifier:

```
<lido:objectPublishedID/>
```

instead of

```
<lido:objectPublishedID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099"  
lido:pref="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00170">  
  https://d-nb.info/gnd/4739509-6  
</lido:objectPublishedID>
```

- no revision history stated:

```
<tei:revisionDesc/>
```

Causes:

- Human error: Inattention
- Metadata elements are not mandatory or missing at all
- The software does not warn the user when mandatory elements are missing
- Lack of time
- Legal issues, e.g., log files of acquisition software must not be published
- The institution does not want to disclose internal procedures and habits to the public

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect, describe

Identification:

- Check if (obligatory) metadata elements or statements are missing or left empty

Target state: All obligatory metadata elements or statements should be existent and filled in with correct information. Also, any metadata that could help understand, assess, or use the data that can lawfully be published should be included in the data.

DATA01.1.7 Lack of rights statement and/or license

Description: It is unclear which rights are tied to single data records if it is not stated directly in the data. Generally, for different data records, distinct rights are mandatory.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (required metadata affects the completeness of data elements of the domain of interest)

Other affected quality features:

- external completeness (right holders and licenses are typically available as links, thus missing links affect completeness)
- compliance (rights statement and license information are standard information of the domain of interest)
- availability (missing licenses reduce reusability and thus availability)

Impact on data quality: Data records without a rights statement and/or license cannot be used being further publication, research, etc. Thus this is less valuable for other researchers, journalists, etc. or even unusable.

Examples:

- rights completely missing:

```
<lido:rightsHolder/>
```

instead of

```
<lido:rightsHolder>
  <lido:legalBodyID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099"
    lido:source="ISIL (ISO 15511)">
    https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-Mb112
  </lido:legalBodyID>
  <lido:legalBodyName>
    <lido:appellationValue>
      Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte - Bildarchiv Foto
      Marburg
    </lido:appellationValue>
  </lido:legalBodyName>
  <lido:legalBodyWeblink>
    https://www.uni-marburg.de/de/fotomarburg
  </lido:legalBodyWeblink>
</lido:rightsHolder>
```

Causes:

- No respective element/statement for providing rights and licenses in the data model
- Human error: Providing rights is forgotten during data acquisition
- The legal situation is unclear due to the current status

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, Collect

Identification:

- Check for empty elements/malformed statements if providing rights and licenses is possible
- No elements/statements available

Target state: Every data record should hold information about its legal status and conditions of reuse.

DATA01.1.8 No rating of a source in the data

Description: Some sources of information are more trustworthy or convincing in their reasoning than others, but these gradations are not directly reflected in the data.

Mainly affected quality feature: trustworthiness (missing reasonable information about the sources affects plausibility)

Other affected quality features:

- provenance (non-convincing information could also be caused by missing verifiable information about its origin)
- internal completeness (missing expected information affects completeness in the context of reasonable information)

Impact on data quality: If all sources are treated equally, although some are more trustworthy/relevant/... than others, implicit knowledge of cataloging persons is not made explicit. Furthermore, users cannot be sure which ones are "the right ones", i.e., the reliable sources used during the data creation. This decreases the understandability and trustworthiness of the data.

Examples:

- A statement published in a widely accepted research journal is more trustworthy than a statement taken from Wikipedia
- The reasoning for a painting's dating introduced in paper A is more convincing than the one in paper B

Causes:

- The data model does not provide a rating of a source
- The staff wants to avoid taking up a position due to lack of knowledge/undecidable cases/political reasons/...

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Sources are provided without an attribute/relation that weighs them.

Target state: In cases where data acquirers can only provide a source of information with a low degree of trustworthiness, this should be emphasized. Otherwise, the data suggests a level of trustworthiness/certainty, ... that does not meet reality. In case different opinions about a fact exist, these should also be outlined in the data, but the more trusted one(s) should be marked to ensure the traceability of the information.

DATA01.2 Unmarked multilingualism

Description: In a dataset, several languages are used for the same field without marking the respective language.

Mainly affected quality feature: appropriateness (multiple languages reduce understandability)

Other affected quality features:

- versatility (since languages are different forms of cultural viewpoints)
- syntactic accuracy (multiple languages in the same field could violate conformity with the description language, i.e., if the repeatability of the element should be used for multilingualism and/or the language information is required as a property of the element)
- coherence (information in multiple languages is standard information that has to be distinguished)
- compliance (usually, there is a standard or a convention that defines how to handle multiple languages)

Impact on data quality: While it is technically correct and desirable to provide descriptions and labels in different languages, not marking which language is used leads to heterogeneous data. Also, applications using the data depend on this information for correct localization.

Examples:

- Measurement types width and "breite" (german for width) in another record of the dataset without an @xml:lang to specify different languages:

```
<lido:measurementType>Breite</lido:measurementType>  
and  
<lido:measurementType>width</lido:measurementType>
```

Causes:

- Default language unclear
- Human error: Attribute or predicate was forgotten
- The data model could not express multilingualism

Root in the data life cycle: Pan, collect

Identification:

- Probably by chance in most cases, especially when data is indexed in several languages.
- A (semi-)automatic approach may prove difficult since there are several options to express something, so a search, e.g., German words might not yield any results because the wrong wording has been chosen in the query.

Target state: A default language for the dataset should be defined. Labels and descriptions in other languages must be marked as such, e.g., by an attribute or an additional statement.

DATA01.3 Heterogeneous data

DATA01.3.1 Heterogeneous structural representations

Description: The same information is represented in structurally heterogeneous forms. This problem often occurs when integrating data from multiple sources.

Mainly affected quality feature: coherence (similar data elements should have similar values)

Other affected quality features:

- compliance (heterogeneous elements could violate standards, conventions, or rules that reduce heterogeneous forms)
- syntactic accuracy (heterogeneous structural forms can violate syntactic validity)
- appropriateness (different structures reduce understandability)

Impact on data quality:

- Data records are not as suitable for further use as they could be since applications processing them have to test for different structures, available data elements, etc.

Examples:

- A measurement value is represented as a result of an event in some cases and as an attribute of an object in other cases:

```
<lido:objectMeasurementsSet>
  <lido:displayObjectMeasurements>Höhe x Breite: 130 x 110 cm
</lido:displayObjectMeasurements>
  <lido:objectMeasurements>
    <lido:measurementsSet>
      <lido:measurementType>Höhe x Breite</lido:measurementType>
      <lido:measurementUnit>cm</lido:measurementUnit>
      <lido:measurementValue>130 x 110</lido:measurementValue>
    </lido:measurementsSet>
  </lido:objectMeasurements>
</lido:objectMeasurementsSet>
```

vs.

```
<lido:eventObjectMeasurements>
  <lido:displayObjectMeasurements>Höhe x Breite: 130 x 110 cm
</lido:displayObjectMeasurements>
  <lido:objectMeasurements>
    <lido:measurementsSet>
      <lido:measurementType>Höhe x Breite</lido:measurementType>
      <lido:measurementUnit>cm</lido:measurementUnit>
      <lido:measurementValue>130 x 110</lido:measurementValue>
    </lido:measurementsSet>
  </lido:objectMeasurements>
</lido:eventObjectMeasurements>
```

Causes:

- [MODEL04](#)
- [DATA09.1](#)
- Dynamics in data model: Different versions of the model are used
- The scope of the acquisition context changes
 - Institution-specific practices
 - Varying research questions which influence on acquisition practices (project context)

Root in the data life cycle: Collect, Integrate

Identification:

- Identify [MODEL04](#) and [DATA09.1](#) representing the same meaning and check if more than one representation is used in the data via existence patterns and regex

- Compare number of occurrences of suspicious structural constructs between the datasets that are to be integrated

Target state: Information should be represented in a uniform way.

DATA01.3.2 Heterogeneous precision of data

Description: For individual data fields, the precision of the value in the dataset varies greatly. So the problem lies in the heterogeneity of the precision, not the imprecision itself (as described in [DATA06.2](#)).

Mainly affected quality feature: coherence (similar data elements should have similar values)

Other affected quality features:

- precision (heterogeneous precision includes inaccurate values. This affects precision)
- compliance (possible violation of standards, conventions, and rules)

Impact on data quality: Applications and analyses based on the data may become difficult since the data is not comparable. Also, data may be too vague/disparate to be useful.

Examples:

- Two dates where the first example has a low precision and the last one is very precise:

```
<lido:event>
  <lido:eventDate>
    <lido:date>
      <lido:earliestDate lido:type="approximate">1553</lido:earliestDate>
      <lido:latestDate lido:type="approximate">1633</lido:latestDate>
    </lido:date>
  </lido:eventDate>
</lido:event>
```

vs.

```
<lido:event>
  <lido:eventDate>
    <lido:date>
      <lido:earliestDate>2002-10-12</lido:earliestDate>
      <lido:latestDate>2002-10-12</lido:latestDate>
    </lido:date>
  </lido:eventDate>
</lido:event>
```

Causes:

- Human errors / missing knowledge of cataloger (e.g., when setting genres)
- Sources for statements too vague / general lack of knowledge (e.g., no research conducted yet)
- Changes in acquisition contest (e.g., different research questions of different projects)
- [DATA04.1](#)

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- If applicable: By attributes or statements marking the degree of precision
- REGEX looking for certain expressions marking a varying degree of precision (e.g. "approx.")

Target state: All data records are available with the same precision.

DATA01.3.3 Heterogenous qualifiers of uncertainty

Description: Different qualifiers are used to indicate a certain degree or type of uncertainty inherent in a piece of information.

Mainly affected quality feature: coherence (lack of consistency with similar data elements and values and lack of comparability)

Other affected quality features:

- compliance (the degree and type of uncertainty should be given by the standards, conventions, or rules)
- appropriateness (different types or missing guidelines of uncertainty reduce understandability)

Impact on data quality: Using different qualifiers to mark a certain degree or type of uncertainty leads to heterogeneous data and loss of consistency since a user or a script parsing the data cannot be sure what the exact meaning of a qualifier is. Due to the heterogeneity, the data is also less precise because not all cases of a specific level of uncertainty might be retrieved in a query. Furthermore, the semantics of the qualifiers are obscured, which leads to a drop in the understandability of the data.

Examples:

- "1920?" vs. "1920(?)" vs. "1920*"

```
<lido:date>  
  <lido:earliestDate>1920?</lido:earliestDate>  
  <lido:latestDate>1920(?)</lido:latestDate>  
</lido:date>
```
- "approx. 1920" vs. "ca. 1920"

```
<lido:date>  
  <lido:earliestDate>approx. 1920</lido:earliestDate>  
  <lido:latestDate>ca. 1920</lido:latestDate>  
</lido:date>
```

Causes:

- No acquisition guide or controlled vocabulary available where qualifiers are defined
- Heterogeneity because different disciplines and their respective customs ("In our domain, '*' is used for...")
- Changes of acquisition contest (e.g., different research questions of different projects)

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: REGEX

Target state: If qualifiers are used, it should be in a controlled way, i.e., each qualifier should have its own clear semantics, outlined by definition. Preferably, degrees of uncertainty should be expressed in a structured way via a controlled vocabulary, cf. [DATA06.7.1](#).

DATA01.3.4 Heterogeneous value representations

Description: In free text fields, heterogeneous styles, phrases, etc., are used, which have the same meanings for describing the same phenomenon.

Mainly affected quality feature: coherence (lack of consistency with similar data elements and values and lack of comparability)

Other affected quality features:

- compliance (possible violation of standards, conventions, or rules)
- appropriateness (different types of information structures reduce understandability)

Impact on data quality:

- Inefficient retrieval: Data records are not able to be found by searching for certain descriptions
- Decrease in comparability and understandability

Examples:

- heterogeneous place name values

```
<lido:namePlaceSet>
  <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">in Rome</lido:appellationValue>
  <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="it">Roma, Italia</lido:appellationValue>
  <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">in der Stadt, Rom, Italien, Europa
</lido:appellationValue>
</lido:namePlaceSet>
```

- heterogeneous display date values

```
<lido:displayDate>im 3. Jhd. n. Chr.</lido:displayDate>
<lido:displayDate>im 3. Jahrhundert AD</lido:displayDate>
<lido:displayDate>im dritten Jahrhundert nach Christus</lido:displayDate>
```

- "lobby" vs. "foyer"

Causes:

- No arrangements between multiple data acquirors (e.g., missing guidelines)
- Changes of acquisition contest (e.g., dif, leading to a drop in the data's understandability)

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Synonym phrases in the same data field of different data records

Target state: Specific phenomena are expressed consistently using similar phrases.

DATA02 Wrong data values

Problems based on faulty data.

DATA02.1 Spelling errors

Description: There are mistakes in the spelling of individual words.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (incorrect spelling of words violates conformance with the language used)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (wrong spelling reduces understandability)
- syntactic accuracy (spelling errors mostly lead to syntactic inaccuracy)

Impact on data quality: Non-human-readable or non-machine-understandable data. In some cases, a misspelling can also alter the meaning of a word entirely so that the information content of a record decreases.

Examples:

- Deformed data type literals
- Misspelled labels

```
<lido:objectWorkType>  
  <skos:Concept>  
    <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">runnen</skos:prefLabel>  
  </skos:Concept>  
</lido:objectWorkType>
```

Instead of

```
<lido:objectWorkType>  
  <skos:Concept>  
    <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Brunnen</skos:prefLabel>  
  </skos:Concept>  
</lido:objectWorkType>
```

Causes: Typing error by catalogers or overlooked during redaction.

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Data field entries do not exist in reference work like dictionaries or lexica.

Target state: All data field entries are spelled correctly. Exceptions are fields that include deliberately wrong values, like inscriptions with mistakes or historical spellings.

DATA02.2 Incorrect information

Description: The information given in the data does not correspond to true scientific facts or other true information. This usually happens during the information acquisition process by the person entering the data.

Mainly affected quality feature: semantic accuracy (incorrect information given)

Other affected quality features:

Impact on data quality: There are wrong statements in the data. Within the database, this can generate inconsistencies while researchers and data users are confronted with errors. This can promote false knowledge and misconceptions, which partially cannot be resolved in the future.

Examples:

- One mistake in the Bildindex took over cultural literature, and even when it got corrected, it still prevailed.

Causes:

- Data sources with wrong information, e.g., wrong license information:

```
<lido:rightsType>  
  <skos:Concept>  
    <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">Free access and reuse</skos:prefLabel>
```

vs

```
  <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Rechte vorbehalten</skos:prefLabel>  
</skos:Concept>  
</lido:rightsType>
```

- Data aging (data becomes outdated)
- Bad estimations or confusion during acquisition
- Missing accuracy by catalogers
- The low professional expertise of catalogers

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Information is stated falsely in data. An active search is nearly impossible since data seems correct at first glance without expert knowledge about the entity itself.

Target state: All given information is correct.

DATA02.3 Incorrect use of controlled vocabulary / authority file

Description: A term of a controlled vocabulary or an entity of an authority file is incorrectly linked in the data (i.e., does not correspond to reality).

Mainly affected quality feature: external accuracy (incorrect references to vocabularies affect external accuracy)

Other affected quality features:

- external completeness (incorrect references to vocabularies affect interlinking completeness)
- data currency (references that become wrong are closely linked to outdated information)
- compliance (use of controlled vocabulary are common in the community and is often part of best practices and rules)
- semantic accuracy (wrong linking does not represent correct values)

Impact on data quality:

If a wrong term for a concept (e.g., a genre) is used the data contradicts reality and is incorrect. This may induce users to trust the data (or worse: All data provided) less. Also, this leads to the wrong information being spread.

Examples:

- Reference where <http://obg.vocnet.org/x001200x> points to "Schabkunst" instead of "Kupferstich"

```
<lido:classification>
  <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/identifier_type/uri">
    http://obg.vocnet.org/x001200x
  </lido:conceptID>
  <lido:term>Kupferstich</lido:term>
</lido:classification>
```

Causes:

- Human error (time pressure, inattentiveness, typos, ...)
- Lack of knowledge
- Different rules for catalogers

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Manual
- Comparison of basic values to values of the referenced data (when not only the reference is given, but additionally basic information, which should match data of the linked record).

Target state: Every use of a controlled vocabulary and/or authority file should precisely match the knowledge about an entity.

DATA02.4 Incorrectly placed information

Description: The information is placed in the wrong data field in the data model. Therefore the information does not match the field description.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (Community rules and handouts may dictate the type and location of information)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (misplaced information reduces the understandability of the data record)
- coherence (if the element is used correctly in other data of the dataset, inconsistencies exist)
- semantic accuracy (misplaced information does not represent correct values)
- external accuracy (if the misplaced information is placed by a link)

Impact on data quality: The statement made in the data is incorrect as the given value does not correspond to the kind of information expected for this field. Therefore information cannot be found even though they are specified in the data. It is not possible to find out if another field should hold this value or which other value would be correct in this field.

Examples:

- where the creator's name has been placed in an element describing a field

```
<lido:namePlaceSet>  
  <lido:appellationValue>Leonardo da Vince</lido:appellationValue>  
</lido:namePlaceSet>
```

- using `tei:name` instead of `tei:date`

```
<tei:name>2019-10-10</tei:name>
```

instead of

```
<tei:date>2019-10-10</tei:date>
```

Causes:

- Different rules for catalogers
- Mistakes during data acquisition (caused by lack of time, knowledge, inattentiveness)
 - Human error (time pressure, and inattentiveness, ...)
 - Lack of knowledge
 - Data model too complex or ambiguous
- Faulty data transformation
- Incomplete data model: The required or desired information aspects do not fit in any specified field
- Data model too complex or ambiguous
- [MODEL02](#)

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Data does not match the format (data type, structure, vocabulary) of the field

- Anomaly detection: The format of the statement differs from other statements in this field
- Search manually

Target state: All information is placed in the designated data field.

DATA02.4.1 Multiple units of information in a single repeatable field

Description: Instead of coding data into repeatable fields, all information is entered into one field with some delimiters. (Note: If the field is not repeatable, there is a data model quality problem ([MODEL01](#)))

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (multiple pieces of information in individual fields violate community rules or handouts if the field is to be repeated)

Other affected quality features:

- syntactic accuracy (multiple information is not correct due to the model)
- appropriateness (misuse of fields reduces understandability)

Impact on data quality: The information increments are not machine-readable without explicitly defining the delimiter.

Examples:

- A repository location in two different languages in one field:

```
<lido:repositoryLocation>München/Munich</lido:repositoryLocation>
```

Causes:

- Faulty data acquisition

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification: Search in fields by the use of delimiters (" ", ";", "/", "|")

Target state:

- When multiple information match in a field, it should be repeatable
- In repeatable fields, the information should never be put into single fields

DATA02.5 Inconsistencies based on dependencies

Problems caused by inconsistencies in dependencies between several values. This violates general plausibility rules. These plausibility rules can be viewed as constraints of the data model.

DATA02.5.1 Non-matching date dependencies

Description: Due to causality and a linear timeline, some events are related to other events and can, therefore, only take place at certain time intervals that depend on different dates. The dependent dates, however, are outside the logical and possible time intervals.

Mainly affected quality feature: logical consistency (date dependencies lead to logical contradictions)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (mismatching dependencies are probably caused by wrong information)
- time concurrency (if some parts of data were updated and other parts were not)

Impact on data quality:

- Contradicting information
- [DATA01.3](#)

Examples:

- Date of death before the birth date:

```
<lido:actor>
```

Date of birth:

```
<lido:vitalDatesActor lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00786">
  <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1955-1-1
  </lido:earliestDate>
  <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1955-1-1
  </lido:latestDate>
</lido:vitalDatesActor>
```

Date of death:

```
<lido:vitalDatesActor lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00787">
  <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1950-1-1
  </lido:earliestDate>
  <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1950-1-1
  </lido:latestDate>
</lido:vitalDatesActor>
<lido:actor>
```

- Artist's creative period is stated outside the artist's lifetime
- The time of an object's creation is outside its creator's lifetime
- Purchase date before creation date
- Purchase date outside the lifetime of the buyer
- Date before the development of technique (e.g., photography earlier than 1826)

Causes:

- Human error
- Contradictory literature sources
- No plausibility check on data input
- Data might partly be not up to date

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Comparison-Pattern (Values)

Target state: Dates stated in the data record should be plausible according to all accompanying information.

DATA02.5.2 Non-matching functional dependencies of categorizations

Description: If fields specify other fields (and therefore contain more specific values), these form a functional dependency. Here, inconsistencies can easily occur if values do not fulfill the requirements resulting from the dependency. This is especially the case for sub-categorizations: Each more specific classification must always have a specific broader classification.

Mainly affected quality feature: logical consistency (contradiction)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (at least one value is wrong)
- trustworthiness (contradictions reduce the understandability of the dataset)

Impact on data quality:

- No matching information
- [DATA01.3](#)

Examples:

- Genre → classification → term → technique (e.g., architecture and photography)
- The profession of artist ↔ genre
- A church is always classified as architecture

Causes:

- Human error
- No plausibility check on data input
- Unclear/blurred facts
- Confusion about combinations of object genres

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Contained-Pattern: Value must be in the list of allowed values, dependent on other value

Target state: All information does match consistently

DATA02.5.3 Non-matching dependencies of spatial statements

Description: The specified locations in data records are linked to other values, which can lead to contradictions.

Mainly affected quality feature: logical consistency (possible contradictions)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (contradictions reduce accuracy)

Impact on data quality:

- Mismatching information
- [DATA01.3](#)

Examples:

- Object: Place of origin + Time of origin ↔ Place of artist
- Place of part-object ↔ Place of total object (Eiffel Tower is not in Rome)

```
<lido:partOfPlace>
  <lido:placeID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">
    http://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q220
  </lido:placeID>
  <lido:namePlaceSet>
    <lido:appellationValue
      lido:pref="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00169" xml:lang="en">
      Rome
    </lido:appellationValue>
  </lido:namePlaceSet>
</lido:partOfPlace>
  <lido:placeID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">
    https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q243
  </lido:placeID>
  <lido:namePlaceSet>
    <lido:appellationValue
      lido:pref="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00169"
      xml:lang="en">
      Eiffel Tower
    </lido:appellationValue>
  </lido:namePlaceSet>
</lido:partOfPlace>
```

Causes:

- Human Error
- No plausibility check on data input
- Unclear/blurred facts

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Plausibility checks

Target state: All spatial information do match consistently

DATA02.5.4 Violation of dependencies between mandatory statements

Description: If a condition is fulfilled (e.g., certain fields are (not) filled in), other fields are mandatory.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (missing information depending on other information violates completeness)

Other affected quality features:

- syntactic accuracy (a data model usually controls these conditions)
- external completeness (if the other mandatory conditions that need to be filled are references)

Impact on data quality: Missing values at mandatory fields

Examples:

- A specified measurement value without type or unit

```
<lido:measurementsSet>  
  <lido:measurementType></lido:measurementType>  
  <lido:measurementUnit></lido:measurementUnit>  
  <lido:measurementValue>203</lido:measurementValue>  
</lido:measurementsSet>
```

Causes: ignorance, faulty sources

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Non-existent pattern (under the condition that another value is (not) set)

Target state: Mandatory fields are always filled with a value. If a field is mandatory to be set under a fixed condition, this condition is met.

DATA03 Duplicate information in data

This section deals with all cases where information occurs more than once in a dataset.

DATA03.1 Multiple data elements describing the same entity

Description: There are at least two data elements or records that describe the same real-life entity.

These are difficult to identify and merge. A proximity metric is required for identification.

Merging is particularly problematic since (even small) differences in the datasets must be checked for accuracy to decide which version to keep. In the best case, all versions are retained, while all but one version is marked as obsolete or incorrect.

Mainly affected quality feature: compactness (multiple pieces of information logically reduce compactness)

Other affected quality features: -

Impact on data quality:

- There can be differences between the data records
 - Hence it is not clear which one is correct
- Updates in data records will only be applied to one. This will lead to contradictions and inconsistencies
- References to one entity may lead to different data records

Examples:

- LIDO lido:lidoRecID is designed to use unique identification in the local system. Database merges and integration processes often generate objects with the same id.

```
<lido:lidoRecID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100"  
  lido:source="Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte - Bildarchiv Foto  
  Marburg">  
  DE/lido/obj20344012  
</lido:lidoRecID>
```

and

```
<lido:lidoRecID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100"  
  lido:source="Zentrale Kustodie - Georg-August-Universität Göttingen">  
  DE/lido/obj20344012  
</lido:lidoRecID>
```

- Two data records with different IDs describing the same painting

Causes:

- catalogers are not aware of existing data records
 - Lack of time for research
- catalogers are not able to identify that a new record describes the very same entity
- Imports from different databases
- Different views/opinions on content
- The entity was acquired under different research questions, which results in a data record for each objective

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Compare different data records with a proximity metric.

Target state: Each real-world entity has only a maximum of one associated data record in the database. When data records are merged from multiple sources, all information should be maintained while one record should be marked as the preferred one. False or outdated information should be marked as such. Merged data records should be preserved to maintain the resolvability of references and a cross-reference to the preferred record should be made.

DATA03.2 Redundancies in data

Description: Redundant data: Information is given in more than one location in a data record/set.

Mainly affected quality feature: compactness (multiple pieces of information logically reduce compactness)

Other affected quality features: -

Impact on data quality:

- Larger data records
- Changes may not be applied to all respective fields equally

Examples:

- unit and the value is redundant because both types address width in two different languages:

```
<lido:measurementsSet>
  <lido:measurementType xml:lang="en">width</lido:measurementType>
  <lido:measurementUnit xml:lang="en">mm</lido:measurementUnit>
  <lido:measurementValue>222</lido:measurementValue>
</lido:measurementsSet>
<lido:measurementsSet>
  <lido:measurementType>Breite</lido:measurementType>
  <lido:measurementUnit>mm</lido:measurementUnit>
  <lido:measurementValue>222</lido:measurementValue>
</lido:measurementsSet>
```

Causes:

- A field is falsely assigned multiple times
- The same information fits into different fields of the record
- Data model calls for redundancies, e.g., when stating information in different languages
- Lack of time for data acquirers which leads to inattentiveness

Root in the data life cycle: Collect, assure

Identification: Same content in multiple fields of a single record.

Target state: Information should be stated only once per data record and dataset.

DATA04 Units of data values

Problems related to units of data values.

DATA04.1 Inconsistent use of units or metric systems

Description: In a measurement entry, units are needed for understandability. Several different units are used depending on the context ([DATA01.3](#)). This makes the comparison more complex because conversion is required. However, values can be converted to use a different unit. With only a single unit, the data would be comparable without conversion. Therefore, using only one metric system and as few units as possible is desirable. In the best case, only SI²⁰-based units are used. (If only one unit is allowed, this can be used as the default unit. No unit needs to be specified in this case's data, and Problem [DATA04.2](#) would not apply. Generally, the unit is not specified or the data model even prevents specification.)

Mainly affected quality feature: coherence (similar measurements should have similar data units)

Other affected quality features:

- versatility (various measurement types in the same entry reduce the possibility of transforming them)

Impact on data quality: Bad comparability

Examples:

- meter instead of centimeter, even if the sizes are similar

```
<lido:measurementsSet>
  <lido:measurementType>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q35059">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">width</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:measurementType>
  <lido:measurementUnit>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q174728">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">centimetre</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:measurementUnit>
  <lido:measurementValue>314</lido:measurementValue>
</lido:measurementsSet>
<lido:measurementsSet>
  <lido:measurementType>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q208826">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">height</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:measurementType>
  <lido:measurementUnit>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q11573">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">metre</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:measurementUnit>
  <lido:measurementValue>2,03</lido:measurementValue>
</lido:measurementsSet>
```

- "9144 m" instead of "10000 Inch"; 0,9 m instead of 1 Yard

Causes: no specifications during data acquisition

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: In different field instances, different units are used

Target state: Only SI base units are used when providing measurements.

²⁰ International System of Unit: <https://www.bipm.org/en/measurement-units/>

DATA04.2 Missing units of measurement

Description: A unit relates a number to other numbers. A numeral value without a unit (except counts) does not provide useful information.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (a number without a unit is not complete)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (a unit without a number is not correct)
- appropriateness (missing units reduce understandability)
- compliance (measurement units logically need units due to rules or guidelines)
- precision (the information is not precise)
- versatility (without units, the information cannot be transformed)

Impact on data quality: A number, e.g., a measurement without units, is not clear. The information is not understandable and hardly usable.

Examples:

- LIDO measurements value without unit

```
<lido:measurementsSet>
  <lido:measurementType>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q35059">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">width</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:measurementType>
  <lido:measurementUnit></lido:measurementUnit>
  <lido:measurementValue>314</lido:measurementValue>
</lido:measurementsSet>
```

- Measurement values like "28,5", "660", "13,7"

Causes: employee forgets specification of units during data acquisition

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: MATCH-Pattern

Target state: Numeric information should always be provided with a unit (if it is not specifying a quantity)

DATA05 References to other datasets

This section includes references to other datasets and relationships of an object to another expressed in the data.

Examples:

- Art → Artist
- Picture ↔ Data record
- dataset → Authority data

DATA05.1 Missing references between data records

Description: A data record describing an entity does not contain references to other records describing related entities. Thus, relationships between entities are not reflected in the data.

Mainly affected quality feature: external completeness (not all relevant links are provided)

Other affected quality features: internal completeness (if the reference is missing within a dataset)

Impact on data quality: The domain of interest is incompletely represented in the data, which results in low data quality. Also, the usability of the records is reduced since the data record is isolated instead of being connected to other data. This impedes making connections to other data (semi-)automatically.

Examples:

- Specifying an actor without providing an URI pointing to an authority file:

```
<lido:actor lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00163">
  <lido:nameActorSet>
    <lido:appellationValue>Botticelli, Sandro</lido:appellationValue>
  </lido:nameActorSet>
</lido:actor>
```

- Missing <lido:relatedWork>
- The connection between entities is described in a free text field but not in a machine-readable way

Causes:

- The person editing the data record was not aware of relations to other entities represented in the dataset or forgot to add the references
- The person acquiring data does not know how to express a relationship between data records
- The data model does not allow to express the relation
- Acquisition software/technology does not allow to express the relation

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- (semi-) automatically identify empty reference fields (if applicable)

Target state: Any relations between entities that exist and/or are described in the data should also be represented in the data (preferably in a machine-readable way).

DATA05.2 Reference to a non-existent data record

Description: A record contains a reference to another record in the same or a different dataset.

However, the referenced record does not (no longer) exist. This may also apply to a reference to norm data.

Mainly affected quality feature: external completeness (not all relevant information is given)

Other affected quality features:

- internal completeness (if the non-existent data record is within the dataset)
- external accuracy (if non-valid links cause the non-existence)
- trustworthiness (non-valid links logically reduce plausibility)

Impact on data quality: Information about the related data record is missing. References cannot be resolved and are unclear, thus impeding further use of the still-existing record.

Examples:

- Identifying a place where the reference refers to nothing:

```
<lido:partOfPlace>  
  <lido:placeID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/identifier_type/uri">  
    http://sws.geonames.org/abcd/  
  </lido:placeID>  
  <lido:namePlaceSet>  
    <lido:appellationValue>Göttingen</lido:appellationValue>  
  </lido:namePlaceSet>  
</lido:partOfPlace>
```

Causes:

- Typo during manual input of the foreign key / ID
- Record has been deleted or moved
- After the removal of duplicate records, the references have not been updated

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Check all references between records regarding the existence of the referenced record or norm data. This should be done regularly, e.g., once a year.

Target state: All records or entries in norm data referenced in a data record should exist and be resolvable.

DATA05.3 Ambiguous reference to a data record

Description: The field of a record, which is used to reference the record within other records and thus should act as a unique identifier, does not have unique values in all records in the dataset.

Mainly affected quality feature: logical consistency (multiple records with the same identifier can lead to consistency problems)

Other affected quality features:

- syntactic accuracy (a reference should be unique by definition)
- external accuracy (if the link is not valid)
- external completeness (non-unique links decrease completeness of linked information)
- internal completeness (if the ambiguous reference is within the dataset)
- availability (non-unique identifiers can cause non-availability of the record and its information)
- compactness (multiple used IDs that are intended to be unique affect compactness)

Impact on data quality: References to other records cannot be evaluated unambiguously. This way, the reference is not resolvable, which leads to a decrease in information content.

Examples:

- LIDO lido:lidoRecID is designed for using unique identification in the local system instead of a generic institution. Database merges and integration processes often generate objects with the same id:

```
<lido:lidoRecID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100"
  lido:source="Zentrale Kustodie - Georg-August-Universität Göttingen">
  DE/lido/obj20344012
</lido:lidoRecID>
and
<lido:lidoRecID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100"
  lido:source="Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte - Bildarchiv Foto
  Marburg">
  DE/lido/obj20344012
</lido:lidoRecID>
```

- A repeatable element relation between object and artist is defined via his/her name (which is not unique) instead of referencing the (object's or) artist's data record ID

Causes:

- A non-unique property of the entity is used for referencing the record
- Inadequate ID management
- Import of records with IDs overlapping those of records already included in the dataset
- [MODEL10](#)

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification: Check the uniqueness of the values in all identifier fields.

Target state: Other records should be referenced via unique identifiers. For this being the case, records should provide an identifier that is unique in the dataset.

DATA05.4 Ambiguous reference to described (real) entity

Description: The reference to the entity described by the data is ambiguous, i.e., it is not specified which entity the data record describes. Several different entities may fall within the scope. In contrast to [DATA05.3](#), the focus here is on references to the entities described by the data, not on references to other data records.

Mainly affected quality feature: external accuracy (ambiguous references to information reduce the accuracy of the information)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (ambiguous links to information reduce understandability)
- compliance (if a reference is required, this information should also be exact and not ambiguous)
- semantic accuracy (ambiguous references that do not match and resolve the required information can resolve wrong information)

Impact on data quality: The referenced entity is not identifiable. This leads to a decrease in information content, and the record is probably less usable since its scope is unclear.

Examples:

- LIDO: Reference to a place only by name while there may be several places with the same name

```
<lido:placeClassification>
  <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://examplePlacesRegister.example/York">
    <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">York</skos:prefLabel>
  </skos:Concept>
</lido:placeClassification>
```

- Reference to the artist only by name, while there may be several artists with the same name

Causes:

- Due to a lack of information, it is unclear which entity is described in the source(s)
- The cataloging persons have yet to be aware of similar entities and the ambiguity of this reference.
- The data model lacks options for referencing authority data
- The data model lacks fields for precisely describing the entity

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Manual test if the real-life entity can be uniquely identified
- Identification may be problematic since there is no way of testing if another object with the same known properties exists.
- Missing references to authority data
- The high number of empty fields

Target state: Each reference to an entity is unambiguous. The entity is identifiable from the reference (value).

DATA05.5 Untraceable resource from URI namespaces

Description: URI namespaces must be chosen with organizational and technical requirements in mind. Unretrievable resources can lead to information loss and data lacks.

Mainly affected quality feature: availability (unretrievable information reduces availability)

Other affected quality features:

- external accuracy (if the link to the resource is available but not valid)
- external completeness (unretrievable resources could lead to information loss)
- appropriateness (unretrievable resources can reduce understandability)

Impact on data quality: In an open, distributed environment, obsolete URIs are essentially useless data values. A single change in a namespace component can confound the validity of large numbers of statements in connected datasets. Altering a chosen namespace severely affects the very purpose of a URI. Resolution of changed URIs can become impossible if no redirecting resolver can be installed and maintained under the old namespace. Even where the redirection is possible, the maintenance overhead for the institution in charge of the namespace, and the burden on those dealing with multiple URIs for a single resource, can be significant.

Examples:

- LIDO: Reference to a place within a reference database like wikidata may change or be deleted. Hence, the link is (temporarily) not retrievable.

```
<lido:placeClassification>
  <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1611098212">
    <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">York</skos:prefLabel>
  </skos:Concept>
</lido:placeClassification>
```

- In 2019, the GND²¹ (Gemeinsame Normdatei) Linked Data Service changed the protocol header in all URIs from http: to https:. Resources under the old URI can still be retrieved, but the new URI replaced the old one as the only "true" identifier. As a consequence, tens of millions of GND URI references that exist throughout the world have essentially become invalid. Any software system not specifically aware of this change will conclude that <http://d-nb.info/gnd/7724415-1> is different from <https://d-nb.info/gnd/7724415-1>. The resulting technical issues are likely to persist for many years to come.

Causes:

- The namespace is based on a non-persistent DNS²² domain, often registered for a project and expiring after the end of the funding period. While still a valid identifier, it usually cannot be made resolvable again. Moreover, an expired domain name can come under the control of a non-related (and sometimes embarrassing) owner.
- The registration of the namespace domain expires for some other reason and is taken over by a domain grabber.
- The namespace is based on the domain name of an external contractor, and this role is taken over by another contractor, or by the institution itself.
- The namespace insinuates an affiliation with an organization. This turns out to be inappropriate for administrative, political, legal, or business reasons.

Root in the data life cycle: Collect, publish

Identification: Ideally, any URI should represent a retrievable resource. This can be verified by simple network requests. Where resolvability is not feasible or necessary, the namespace domain should at least exist in the Internet DNS, and be under the control of the organization that uses the namespace for creating URIs. This can be verified by querying the DNS or a domain registry service.

²¹ <https://www.dnb.de/EN/gnd>

²² DNS = Domain Name System: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Domain_Name_System

Target state: Each reference should be retrievable persistently and standardized using https or persistent identifiers like DOI²³ or handle.

²³ DOI = Digital Object Identifier: ISO 26324:2012(en) Information and documentation — Digital object identifier system <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:26324:ed-1:v1:en>

DATA06 Uncertainty

Some facts cannot be established with certainty due to a lack of knowledge. Based on probabilities, inferences, hints, few data points, etc., the set of possible values may be limited or an assumption may be made.

We consider [DATA01.1](#) as a type of uncertainty.

DATA06.1 Questionable data

Description: Statements in the data may be unreliable in the sense that their semantic correctness is in question. Due to a lack of clear evidence (or aging of the data), there are doubts.

Mainly affected quality feature: trustworthiness (doubtful data without explanations reduces trustworthiness)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (doubtful data might not be correct)
- provenance (if clear and valid references to origin are not given)

Impact on data quality: Data quality is decreased by doubtful data since the information is potentially wrong. However, data quality is improved by qualification and (approximate) quantification of the data's trustworthiness and by giving indications of the source.

Examples:

- Dates in LIDO are often subject to uncertainty but not indicated as such

```
<lido:resourceDateTaken>
  <lido:displayDate>1900?</lido:displayDate>
  <lido:date>
    <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
      1900
    </lido:earliestDate>
    <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
      1900
    </lido:latestDate>
  </lido:date>
</lido:resourceDateTaken>
```

Causes:

- Lack of perfect information during data creation
 - The information is subject to ongoing research and is not yet proven or accepted as definitely correct by the research community
 - There is evidence (e.g., in sources) for a statement to be true with an increased probability but not with 100% certainty
 - Sources, measurements, or clues only implicitly point toward something
 - Multiple measurements have different results
 - Sources are dubious regarding their authenticity or accuracy
 - The reliability of sources is in question
 - Limited trust in sources
 - Only a few sources or measurements available
 - Theories are (still) unproven
 - Interpretation of historical sources
 - The person editing the data record is only certain (or confident) to some extent that the statement s/he makes in the data is true
 - The considered sources
 - Only point in a direction

- Are questionable regarding their authenticity or correctness
- Are extremely subjective or biased
- Are too few to know for certain
- There exist hints contradicting the statement
- The research was performed only partially due to lack a of resources
- Lack of sources
- Unproven assumption(s)
- Providing an estimation (i.e., guess) rather than no statement at all
- Through aging of the data (dynamics), it is uncertain if the data is still up to date and correct (see [DATA07.3](#))

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Institution-specific methods for implicitly or explicitly marking doubtfulness, e.g., by appending "?"
- An imprecise statement could be a hint for the cataloger not being confident enough to make a more precise statement
- Hints in the data concerning the cataloger's level of confidence
- The date of the last modification is long ago
- No or only a few indications of source

Target state: The data should include as much certain information as is available per the current state of research. Information that is not yet accepted as correct by the research community but has an increased probability of being correct should also be included in the data, marked, and qualified appropriately (see [DATA06.7](#)). The same holds for information with an increased probability of being correct that the person editing the record was not (yet) able to verify.

DATA06.2 Imprecision

Description: Statements in the data that do not meet the context-specific requirements for precision.

They need to be more precise for context-specific use cases. The statement implies several possible values on a continuum, of which, at most, one is correct. These values are all coherent according to a similarity measure. They differ only quantitatively. The boundaries of the set of values indicated by the statement may be known unambiguously (e.g., "between 1900 and 1910") or fuzzily (e.g., "around 1905"). Temporal and spatial data are often affected by imprecision. However, verbal statements (e.g., for classifying an object) can also be imprecise and thus too general or abstract.

Mainly affected quality feature: precision (imprecise information affects precision)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (imprecision reduces understandability, e.g., if ranges are unclear)

Impact on data quality:

- The data is of low quality as it is less precise than expected and required by the users.

Examples:

- LIDO dates can be imprecise, e.g., given only the year and not the full date

```
<lido:date>
  <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1900
  </lido:earliestDate>
  <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1900
  </lido:latestDate>
</lido:date>
```

- Acquisition based on an illustration of the object, without access to the actual object
 - Additional uncertainties, estimations, guesses (e.g., material)

Causes:

- Information about the research entity is not exactly but only imprecisely known
 - With the current state of research and with all available sources, only imprecise information can be ascertained (e.g., measured)
 - Information is based on estimation (e.g., via comparison to other related entities and information)
 - Limited precision of measurement tools and analysis methods
 - Non-reproducibility of physical measurements
 - Noise in measurements
- The current state of research is not exactly but only imprecisely mapped to the data
 - During the editing of the data record, precise information cannot be determined (with comparative effort)
 - Only imprecise statements in the considered sources
 - Providing an approximation or guess in order to avoid a missing statement
 - Practice of "certainty rather than precision": Rather giving an imprecise but certain statement than making a precise statement which may be incorrect
 - Dynamics: Statements lacking further contextual information become imprecise over time
- The technology used or the data model does not allow precise statements in the data record or the data model itself contains imprecision
- Authority data is imprecise and thus causes imprecision in the data referencing it

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification:

- Words hinting at estimations (e.g., "ca.")

- Number rounded off (e.g., to an integer)
- The suffix of a number consists of many zeros
- Unit too rough
- An interval is given where a single value is expected
 - Undefined or imprecise interval boundaries (e.g., "after ...")
- Set of discrete possible but mutually exclusive values
- Abstract, too general terms
- Undefined symbols

Target state: The data should meet the context-specific requirements for precision if the current state of research provides this level of precision. Otherwise, imprecision should be explicitly marked and qualified ([DATA06.7](#)).

DATA06.3 Contradiction

Description: There are several contradictory statements in the data. Thus at most, one of the statements can be true. They either give different alternatives for the same information aspect (i.e., field), such as several possible birthdates of an artist or span several different fields and violate a plausibility rule that imposes a constraint over these fields ([DATA02.5](#)). In contrast to [DATA06.2](#) the alternatives are not similar. They differ not only quantitatively but also qualitatively. The contradictions are either accidental or deliberately introduced because no clear statements can be made on the basis of the cataloger's research or even according to the current state of research.

Mainly affected quality feature: logical consistency (contradictions reduce consistency)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (the wrong or both statements affect correctness)
- compliance (Contradictions often arise when dependencies between data values defined in terms of domain rules are ignored)

Impact on data quality: As the statements contradict each other, only one of them can be correct.

Since the user cannot tell which of the given statements is correct, the data quality is decreased.

Examples:

- LIDO date specifications are always indicated with the earliest and latest date, which can cause contradictions

```
<lido:date>
  <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1650
  </lido:earliestDate>
  <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1600
  </lido:latestDate>
</lido:date>
```

- Providing a specific creator for a painting in the metadata and referencing another person as a creator in a free text description

Causes:

- Unintended contradiction:
 - Different persons editing the record have different opinions/interpretations/understandings of the entity of interest and (unknowingly) transfer these to (different parts of) the data without indicating the contradiction explicitly
 - When incorrect statements are updated, thus new correct statements are added, and the old statements are not removed or marked as outdated
 - Human error: Inattentiveness
 - The person editing the record accidentally makes ambiguous statements based on institution-specific practices ([DATA09](#))
- Intended contradiction:
 - Research debate:
 - Multiple researchers disagree on a specific topic
 - Multiple contradicting opinions/sources are reflected in the data
 - The person editing the record based on his/her research identified multiple possible but mutually exclusive values and could not figure out which of the values was correct, so he or she included all of them in the data

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Check plausibility rules via pattern matching

- Detect violations of typical dependencies (e.g., genre and occupation of the associated artist) identified via statistical analysis (e.g., anomaly detection) or machine learning methods
- Field repetition
- Multiple values in a single field (e.g., separated via special characters, such as "," or "|")

Target state: The data should be free of any contradictions except for those that, per the current state of research, represent equally valid, contradicting opinions of researchers and those that represent multiple possible but mutually exclusive values identified but not solved by the person editing the record. These contradictions should be expressed explicitly and augmented with contextual information ([DATA06.7](#)). The data should be updated as soon as there are new findings regarding the topic of discussion.

DATA06.4 Unmarked uncertainties in data

Description: Statements in the data are uncertain (e.g., imprecise, contradictory, unreliable, or incomplete) but are not marked as such.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (uncertain information is important information, if this information is not given, the data is incomplete)

Other affected quality features:

- compliance (there are rules and guidelines available on how to mark uncertainties)
- semantic accuracy (missing information about the uncertainty leads to incorrect information)
- precision (the information is not precise without marked as uncertain)
- appropriateness (unmarked uncertainty increases misunderstandings and therefore reduces understandability of the information)

Impact on data quality: The data users cannot recognize uncertainties in the data and thus are not able to handle the affected information with caution when using them as a basis for their further scientific work. For example, an uncertainty score per record cannot be calculated. Strictly speaking, statements suggesting they are certain when they are incorrect. Missing indications of uncertainties also prevents formalization of uncertainties' semantics and thus (semi-) automatic reduction of uncertainty.

Examples:

- Stating a statue is made in 1700 whereas no exact source for this statement is available and thus the statement is uncertain (i.e., imprecise or a guess)

```
<lido:displayDate>um 1900</lido:displayDate>
```

Causes:

- No guidelines telling the catalogers how to mark uncertainty
- The data model does not allow for marking uncertainty
- Person or institution does not want to lose reputation
- Stems from the uncertainty of the person editing the record or from the current state of research
- It is not specified which type of information is expected for a specific field (e.g., single value or interval). If e.g., an interval is given, the user does not know whether this is a hint for imprecision (interval vs. unknown single value in the interval).

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification:

- Hint: Inconsistencies
- Hint: Incompleteness
- Abstract (verbal) statements
- Imprecise statements hint at the estimation

Target state: Any uncertain statements in the data should be marked and qualified (context) appropriately.

DATA06.5 Implicitly marked uncertainties

Description: Statements in the data are uncertain but only implicitly marked as such. For example, they are marked by additional characters in the same field instead of being specified by additional appropriate constructs. Implicit encodings of uncertainty are institution-specific and often ambiguous. Thus, these encodings could be more understandable. (cf. [DATA01.3.3](#))

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (community guidelines or rules typically define how to mark uncertainties)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (missing explicit information about the uncertainty leads to incorrect information)
- internal completeness (uncertain information is important information that leads to incomplete data)
- syntactic accuracy (implicit information in the form of characters violate accuracy if not prescribed by guidelines)
- appropriateness (implicit information by various constructs reduces understandability)
- versatility (special encodings through characters reduce versatility)

Impact on data quality: Both machines and humans cannot easily understand and assess the uncertainty of the information. This means information about uncertainty cannot easily be queried and appropriately presented to the user. For example, an overall uncertainty score per data record cannot easily be calculated. Implicit tagging also prevents the formalization of the semantics of uncertainties and hence the (semi-)automatic reduction of uncertainty.

Examples:

- A date specification with a character for the uncertainty instead of explicitly marking the uncertainty

```
<lido:displayDate>um 1910?</lido:displayDate>
```

Instead of

```
<lido:date>
  <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00529">
    1900
  </lido:earliestDate>
  <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00529">
    1920
  </lido:latestDate>
</lido:date>
```

Causes:

- The data model or technology does not allow to explicitly expressed uncertainty ([MODEL01](#))
- cataloger does not understand the modeling concepts for expressing uncertainty

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification:

- Patterns: Structural patterns, regular expressions
- Data mining: Anomaly detection

Target state: Any uncertain statements in the data should be expressed explicitly. To achieve this, the underlying data model must allow for expressing any uncertain statements.

DATA06.6 Undescribed dependency between uncertain statements

Description: There is a dependency between several uncertain statements in the data, but the dependency is not (explicitly) specified in the data. This often occurs when several possible but mutually exclusive values are given for a field A, and the value of another field (field B) depends on which of these values is correct for field A.

Mainly affected quality feature: semantic accuracy (lack of explicit information about uncertainty leads to incorrect information)

Other affected quality features:

- internal completeness (uncertain information like dependencies are important information that leads to incomplete data)
- compliance (there should be guidelines or rules on how to mark uncertainties)

Impact on data quality: Since dependencies between statements in the data are not (explicitly) specified, data users are not aware of these dependencies. Thus, users erroneously consider combinations of statements that contradict the dependency rules and thus are incorrect as possibly correct.

Example:

- Values of a location implicitly depend on each other because of hierarchical structure like parts of place but are not indicated as such.

Causes:

- The data model does not allow expressing dependencies between uncertain statements
- Cataloger forgets to add dependency information
- The system for editing records does not allow adding dependencies simply and understandably

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Manually check if there exists an unmarked dependency between multiple uncertain statements of a data record or a set of related records

Target state: Any dependency between uncertain statements should be expressed explicitly in the data.

DATA06.7 Lack of qualification of uncertainty

Description: There are uncertain statements in the data that are not further qualified. Therefore, there is a lack of contextual meta-information about the uncertainty, such as the type of uncertainty, the reason for the uncertainty (e.g., subjective vs. objective, lack of resources, etc.), the level of confidence ([DATA06.7.1](#)), the indication of the source, the expertise of the person editing the record, the length of time the record has been edited, the date of the last modification, etc.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (there should be guidelines or rules on how to mark uncertainties)

Other affected quality features:

- internal completeness (uncertain information is important information that increases incompleteness of data)
- precision (precise information missing regarding reason and type of uncertainty)

Impact on data quality: If context information for uncertain statements is missing from the data, users cannot assess the consequences of using uncertain data as, e.g., they cannot assess the level of trustworthiness or whether they might find certain information elsewhere.

Examples:

- LIDO displayDate is often marked with uncertainty but not further qualified

```
<lido:displayDate>1855?</lido:displayDate>
```

Causes:

- The data model does not allow to express context information for uncertain statements
- cataloger does not enter context information for uncertain statements

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect, describe

Identification:

- Check if the data model supports context information for uncertain statements
- Find empty fields that should hold context information for uncertain statements

Target state: Any uncertain statements should be accompanied by information specifying the context of uncertainty, i.e., the cause for and level of uncertainty. Regarding the cause of uncertainty, we, first of all, need to distinguish between subjective and objective uncertainty (i.e., the *source* of uncertainty). The former is present if the cataloger needs to be certain about a statement she/he makes in the data. Objective uncertainty, in contrast, means that according to the current state of research, no certain statement can be made by any researcher in the field. Furthermore, the *cause* for subjective or objective uncertainty should be specified more precisely via controlled vocabulary. For example, subjective uncertainty may be caused by a lack of time for research when creating a data record. The *level* of uncertainty (or confidence) should be expressed via controlled vocabulary ([DATA06.7.1](#)).

DATA06.7.1 Indeterminate degree of uncertainty

Description: Some statements are more certain than others, but this is not expressed in the data.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (there should be guidelines or rules on how to mark uncertainties)

Other affected quality features:

- internal completeness (coherence is implicitly affected since some statements are implicitly more uncertain than others)
- precision (precise information missing regarding reason and type of uncertainty)

Impact on data quality: When statements have a different degree of certainty, but this is not stated in the data, less certain statements can appear more certain and vice versa. This way, the data suggests (un)certainly where there is none. Thus the data is not correct (in a narrower sense), nor is it precise, and may lead to wrong deductions in reuse. It further prevents the calculation of the overall level of uncertainty per record.

Examples:

- LIDO display date is often marked with different uncertainty but not expressed

```
<lido:displayDate>um 1900?</lido:displayDate>
<lido:date>
  <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00529">
    1900
  </lido:earliestDate>
  <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00529">
    1900
  </lido:latestDate>
</lido:date>
```

VS

```
<lido:displayDate>um 1900?</lido:displayDate>
<lido:date>
  <lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1901
  </lido:earliestDate>
  <lido:latestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00528">
    1899
  </lido:latestDate>
</lido:date>
```

- Hypotheses with strong vs. weak evidence are placed next to each other without differentiation

Causes:

- The data model does not allow for stating different degrees of uncertainty
- Staff cannot determine the proper level of uncertainty

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Lexical analysis of the data fields if different degrees of uncertainty are indicated. Otherwise, cases can only be identified by checking the data manually.

Target state: If a piece of information is not certain, this should be marked and classified according to the degree of uncertainty. The degree of uncertainty should preferably be taken from a controlled vocabulary.

DATA06.8 Heterogeneous representations of uncertainty

Description: Occurrences of a specific type of uncertainty are expressed in several different (i.e., heterogeneous) ways in the data. This concerns both implicit markings via qualifiers ([DATA01.6.3](#)) and explicit representations.

Mainly affected quality feature: coherence (different expressions of uncertainty affect consistency)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (various expression of uncertainty reduces understandability)
- compliance (there should exist rules or guidelines on how to mark uncertainty)

Impact on data quality: Data quality is negatively impacted by heterogeneous representations of a specific type of uncertainty since they must all be taken into account and be processed when humans or machines interpret (or analyze) the data.

Examples:

- 1989? vs. 1989 (?)

```
<lido:displayDate>um 1989?</lido:displayDate>
```

```
<lido:displayDate>um 1989(?)</lido:displayDate>
```

Causes:

- [MODEL04](#)
- [MODEL09](#)
- [DATA01.3.3](#)

Root in the data life cycle: Plan

Identification:

-

Target state: There should be precisely one uniform way to express each type of uncertainty. This should be an explicit representation. This should be an explicit representation.

DATA07 Dynamics

All inventory research data is changeable and never finished, as there can always be new findings. Therefore, existing data may become outdated and need to be changed.

DATA07.1 Undocumented data dynamics (in the data itself)

Description: Due to new information, the values of a data field may change. Older knowledge is often deleted and replaced by newer information, resulting in a loss of information about previous data. Sometimes, however, outdated information is also stored in free text fields.

Mainly affected quality feature: temporal traceability (the changes are not explicitly or not precisely expressed)

Other affected quality features:

- causal traceability (changes should be made with causal dependencies)
- internal completeness (if the outdated information is not marked as outdated)
- time concurrency (if the information in the free text field is not documented as outdated)
- logical consistency (if there is outdated and updated information and not documented as such, they increase logical consistency)

Impact on data quality: Former states of knowledge are lost, which is a loss of information content. Changes are not transparent to the user, which can lead to a severe drop in the data provider's trustworthiness.

Examples:

- https://sammlungen.uni-goettingen.de/lidoresolver?id=record_kuniweb_365457
- https://sammlungen.uni-goettingen.de/objekt/record_kuniweb_365457/1/-/
- The information of a record from the University of Goettingen²⁴ that has changed over the years is just available in the description as free text:

```
<lido:objectDescriptionSet lido:type="description">
  <lido:descriptiveNoteValue>[...] Kirchhoff: Artemis von Ephesus Bisher als "Vielbrüstige"
    bezeichnet. Heutige Deutung: Der Göttin Artemis galt der Stier als heilig, er war ihr
    Begleiter. Nach der Opferung der Stiere wurden der Göttin Girlanden aus Stierhoden
    Umgehängt.
</lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
<lido:sourceDescriptiveNote>Georg-August-Universität Göttingen
</lido:sourceDescriptiveNote>
</lido:objectDescriptionSet>
```

Causes:

- Missing change management
- Data history not expressible in the data model

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: Searching for certain phrases in free text fields. In the case of deleted data, nothing can be done with reasonable effort.

Target state: Changes in data should be addressed explicitly, e.g., as a changelog (cf. TEI).

Alternatively, data fields with outdated information could provide information about their up-to-dateness and a date stamp when the field has been marked as outdated. In XML-based data formats, this could be achieved by attributes (e.g., "currentness='out-of-date' currentness-change='2019-01-01' ", whereas in graph-based formats, two triples/statements

²⁴ Homepage of University collection Göttingen:

<https://hdl.handle.net/21.11107/d0c7a32e-2652-479d-883f-5b51e3fc4bb4> (accessed on 08/04/2020)

https://sammlungen.uni-goettingen.de/lidoresolver?id=record_kuniweb_365457 (accessed on 08/04/2020)

could be added (e.g., "X" "hasCurrentnessStatus" "outdated" and "X" "isOutdatedSince" "2019-01-01").

DATA07.2 Undocumented data changes caused by model dynamics

Description: When the data model changes, the data structure can change or be adopted. However, there are no indications of the history of data changes.

Mainly affected quality feature: temporal traceability (changes to data, for example, through transformations, should be traced in the data)

Other affected quality features:

Impact on data quality: Missing information on model changes is not transparent to the user and might lead to problems in applications using the data. Furthermore, the missing information can be viewed as a lack of information content.

Examples: An element or predicate is renamed in the data model and the data records are updated without any note of it in the data.

Causes:

- The data model does not provide the possibility to provide information on changes due to model updates ([MODEL05](#)), e.g., lidoRecID has changed due to ingesting, but just the newer ID is kept

```
<lido:lidoRecID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100"  
lido:source="Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte - Bildarchiv Foto  
Marburg">  
DE-Mb112/lido/obj20344012  
</lido:lidoRecID>
```

- Human error: Documentation has been forgotten

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, collect

Identification: No elements/statements exist where information about changes in the data model is stored.

Target state: All data records have a revision element/statement wrt. data model updates and resulting changes in the data records.

DATA07.3 Outdated data

Description: Obsolete data has not been edited recently. As updates relating to the entity of interest have not been transferred to the dataset describing the entity, it is possible that the dataset no longer correctly represents the entity. This also applies to cases where formerly uncertain information represented in the data over time solidifies or turns out to be (in)correct. In this case, the dataset must also be updated accordingly. The required frequency of updating depends on the type of entity represented by the data and its volatility.

Mainly affected quality feature: data currency (data update has not been made)

Other affected quality features:

- data update currency (if the information is known as outdated, the longer it is outdated, the more data update currency is affected)
- semantic accuracy (if the information is known as outdated, it does not represent the true facts anymore)
- appropriateness (outdated data reduces understandability logically)

Impact on data quality: Outdated data causes low data quality since the data may not correctly represent the current state of research regarding the described entity. Additionally: If users cannot assess how old the data is (e.g., due to missing information concerning timestamps), it decreases their trust in the accuracy of the data.

Examples:

- Former assumptions that turned out to be false are not marked as such in the data
- The date of creation for artwork is now more precisely known than before because of scientific progress, but this increase in precision is not reflected in the data
- lido:repositorySet with type = "current" where a user cannot be sure if this still holds:

```
<lido:repositorySet lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido01017">  
  <lido:displayRepository>Galleria degli Uffizi (Firenze), Saal 10-14  
  </lido:displayRepository>  
</lido:repositorySet>
```

Causes:

- The research knowledge about entities is growing, the assigned data records have to be updated when new knowledge is gained
- Not enough resources for keeping data up to date
- Changes or updatable information have not been noticed
- No existing workflow for keeping data up to date

Root in the data life cycle: Plan, preserve

Identification:

- Hint: The last update of a record lies further in the past than desired for the specific task
- Hint: Low frequency of data record change

Target state: Each record should describe the current state of research regarding the described entity. The record should be updated as soon as the entity changes or new information is available.

DATA08 Subjectivity

Description: A subjective opinion is presented in the data, i.e., descriptions that are strongly influenced by an opinion are assessed. This can occur in fields with free-text-like descriptions.

Mainly affected quality feature: trustworthiness (subjective information reduces plausibility)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (subjective information does often not represent the true facts)

Impact on data quality: The delivered knowledge is shaped by opinion and therefore not objective.

Examples:

- "beautiful", "ugly", "good", "bad", "fantastic", "cruel" or similar adjectives, e.g., in descriptive notes:

```
<lido:descriptiveNoteValue>  
  [...] The Mona Lisa is the greatest painting by Leonardo da Vinci. [...]  
</lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
```

Causes:

- Bad data acquisition

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Finding judgmental formulations using Containment-Pattern

Target state: The information is collected objectively.

DATA09 Implicit knowledge

Description: Knowledge about the context of data collection is not explicitly expressed in the data and interpretations and background knowledge are required to fully understand the knowledge provided.

Mainly affected quality feature: internal completeness (important information missing to fully understand the information)

Other affected quality features:

- appropriateness (understanding of the information is affected)

Impact on data quality: Data becomes more trustworthy for others if implicit knowledge is (at least partly) communicated. Assessment of the completeness of data is difficult. Data is only partially fit for reuse.

Examples:

- Foto Marburg holds negatives within its collection that need to be documented. Therefore each negative record contains a certain signature with numbers and characters. The character stands for the format of the negative, e.g., LA = 35mm format, B = medium format. So the information on the format is implicit within this information.

```
<lido:resourceMeasurementsSet>  
  <lido:measurementValue>LA</lido:measurementValue>  
</lido:resourceMeasurementsSet>
```

- Context of data collection, e.g., within a certain research project, is only partially derivable from the object number
- Researchers of a project are not interested in the names of bishops within a historical source. For data review, it is important to know that s/he left out bishops' names within the person's vocabulary.
- Data is generated only by and for the use of one researcher within a project.

Causes:

- For local use of data, not everything needs to be made explicit because people generating and using data have implicit knowledge (of the place, collection, scientific context, etc.)
- Human error: Making implicit knowledge explicit has been forgotten
- Lack of time/resources
- Some information is taken as self-evident and, therefore, not expressed explicitly

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Review of Workflow- or Project documentation
- Data that is not explicitly collected can hardly be identified. A qualitative review by a domain expert might give an idea of what is not expressed within the data.

Target state:

- The knowledge that is important for the understanding of data is made explicit.
- Context, background, and origin of the data generated are made explicit.
- Datasets of projects are published with Metadata about the collection process and context.

DATA09.1 Use of non-standardized symbols to express certain facts

Description: During the acquisition, catalogers think up symbols to make their work easier or to communicate with the reviewing person. Free text fields are used for this purpose. The meaning of these symbols is rarely documented and may even change over time, so their meaning may not be clear. They often represent uncertainties about the issue being described. They are usually not known to persons outside the data collection workflow, so the meaning or content of these symbols is hidden at other stages of the data life cycle. This leads to confusion for users at later stages when they look at the data. In addition, the information remains implicit and is not machine-readable. In retrieval systems, the information can hardly be found.

Mainly affected quality feature: appropriateness (the use of non-standardized symbols can be misleading)

Other affected quality features:

- compliance (special characters should always stick with rules, guidelines, or standards)
- coherence (since several catalogers could use different symbols)

Impact on data quality: Values are not unique concerning their semantic meaning. Data is only human-readable and might be outdated. Since information is not explicit, it is not findable via retrieval systems.

Examples:

- The field for Comments is used to discuss questions by marking them with "Q:"

```
<lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
```

```
Die Tritonen wurden 1874 durch Kopien von Luigi Amici ersetzt. Q: Alle Originale befinden sich im Giardino del Lago der Villa Borghese.
```

```
</lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
```

- Comments like "x", "y", "?" = "unknown, please add later"

Causes:

- Incomplete data model: Data does not fit in any field
 - Missing fields to express uncertainties or relations between fields
- Missing documentation of local data-collection practices
- Missing possibilities to communicate within workflow other than via data-fields
- Missing or few quality checks

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: If symbols are known, data fields can be checked for them.

Target state:

- Data models and cataloging software provide machine-readable possibilities to express uncertainties.
- Communication about Work in Progress is done outside the data and cataloging system

DATA10 Controlled vocabulary

DATA10.1 Violation of controlled vocabularies (use of custom values)

Description: When using a controlled vocabulary in certain fields, the value entered must be in a list of allowed values that conforms to the field specification to ensure comparability and uniformity. If the designated vocabulary is ignored, new entries will not be uniform or comparable. This may be the case if new values are used, a vocabulary contains homonymous values, synonymous values which are not in the vocabulary, or spelling errors. Sometimes the new values are automatically included in the controlled vocabulary.

Mainly affected quality feature: syntactic accuracy (If custom values differ from the controlled and reviewed vocabulary value, they are most likely incorrect.)

Other affected quality features:

- coherence (since controlled vocabularies are typically used and the violation of these vocabulary entries are individual cases, consistency is affected)
- external completeness (If vocabularies in the form of links are to be used in the data model and the link does not exist or is invalid, interlinking completeness is affected)
- internal completeness (if the vocabulary is for internal use)
- appropriateness (use of wrong references reduce understandability)

Impact on data quality: Comparability across data records suffers because various terms (preferred/alternative/custom) are used to describe the same entity.

Examples:

- "cup" is intended, but the synonymous value "mug" is used (use of an alternative term instead of the preferred term)

```
<skos:Concept rdf:about="https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q81727">  
  <skos:altLabel xml:lang="en">mug</skos:prefLabel>  
</skos:Concept>
```

- Internal vocabularies can be freely supplemented: E.g., the vocabulary did contain "Druck" and "„Kupferstich (Druck)" for "Sachbegriff 5230".
- "watch" is contained as a clock in the vocabulary, but used in the meaning of "guard"

Causes:

- The *acquisition software* allows for both free text and controlled terms
- Misspelling or ignorance of rules in data generation or revision
- Multiple individuals use the same vocabulary developing their own rules for entries each, i.e., not using the vocabulary correctly
 - Description of controlled terms unclear
- Human error: Use of alternative terms instead of preferred terms
- In LIDO files: The data is not validated with the schema file

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Contained-Pattern: Value must be in the list of allowed values, dependent on other value
- Wrong use of homonymous values needs extensive (manual?) contextual analysis

Target state: All fields/elements/statements that should be controlled using a term of one of the mandatory controlled vocabulary/vocabularies.

DATA10.2 Lack of reference to authority data (global comparability)

Description: The data do not contain references to authority data. Authority data provide unique identifiers for unambiguous reference to a specific entity and contain all relevant information about this entity.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (references to authority data are common practice and defined as mandatory in many rules or guidelines)

Other affected quality features:

- external completeness (references to vocabularies are not complete)
- appropriateness (relevant information should be linked to reduce misunderstandings and improve understandability)

Impact on data quality: References to entities such as persons or places without references to corresponding authority records may be ambiguous as, e.g., a person's name is not unique. Furthermore, it is not possible to reuse information provided by authority data without a proper reference (e.g., as a URI).

Examples:

- Examples of authority data:
 - IconClass for Iconography
 - AAT for Art and Architecture
 - GND for Persons, Corporate Bodies, and Subject Headings
 - TGN for geographical places
- The actor ID in LIDO is not used as a reference

```
<lido:actorID>123456789</lido:actorID>
```

instead of

```
<lido:actorID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/identifier_type/uri">  
http://d-nb.info/gnd/123468493  
</lido:actorID>
```

Causes:

- The authority data needed does not exist
- Technology or data model does not allow to add a reference to authority data
- The person editing the data record does not add the reference to authority data
- Vocabulary is imprecise ([MODEL13.2](#))

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- Fields for referencing authority data are empty

Target state: Data should include as many references to authority data as possible. Ideally, each entity mentioned should be linked to an apt authority file.

DATA10.3 Unnecessary use of a custom controlled vocabulary

Description: The controlled vocabulary used is a custom vocabulary (e.g., specific to an institution), although all the terms included in the custom vocabulary are already included in a widely used and established domain-specific controlled vocabulary.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (it is common practice to use standard vocabularies instead of custom vocabularies)

Other affected quality features:

- external completeness (references to established elements should refer to well-maintained and standardized vocabularies)
- coherence (misuse of references leads to inconsistencies)
- appropriateness (the use of standard vocabulary entries increase understandability)
- data currency (the use of standard vocabulary entries increase currency)
- compactness (institutional vocabularies entries, while there are standard vocabularies entries, affect compactness)
- time concurrency (if part of the elements still uses the custom vocabulary and another part of elements already uses the standard vocabulary)
- internal completeness (if the vocabulary is for internal use)

Impact on data quality: Using custom-made controlled vocabularies while established ones are already at hand significantly decreases the interoperability and, thus, the reusability of data records. A local URI or term has to be mapped to existing vocabularies which impedes applications using data from more than one source.

Examples:

- Use of local vocabulary terms instead of using the existing term of a standard public vocabulary:

```
<lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/identifizier_type/uri">  
  http://some-local-museum.org/Kupferstich  
</lido:conceptID>
```

instead of

```
<lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/identifizier_type/uri">  
  http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300041341  
</lido:conceptID>
```

Causes:

- Lack of knowledge about existing and established controlled vocabularies
- Lack of knowledge about how to reference established controlled vocabularies

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- REGEX for URIs, which test if the URI matches a well-known vocabulary

Target state: All references to a controlled vocabulary should refer to public, well-known, and established controlled vocabularies (if possible). The use (and thus the development) of custom-controlled vocabularies should be restricted to cases where no apt term in a widespread existing vocabulary is at hand.

DATA11 Violation of format specification

Description: Some fields have concrete syntactic specifications for their values. Invalid data in these fields violate these specifications.

Mainly affected quality feature: compliance (if concrete syntactic specification exists, compliance is affected)

Other affected quality features:

- syntactic accuracy (if the information does not conform to the data model, it is not syntactically correct)
- appropriateness (violation of specifications reduce understandability)
- versatility (non-compliance to the data model or guideline specification affects versatility)

Impact on data quality:

- The data are not explicitly readable, neither from employees nor automatically.

Examples:

- Postcode
- street names
- Numbers (binary, decimal, hexadecimal) (Letters, Signs)
- Datings have a fixed format (dd/mm/yyyy; mm/dd/yyyy; yyyy-mm-dd ...)

```
<lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00529">  
4th of July 1995  
</lido:earliestDate>  
Instead of  
<lido:earliestDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00529">  
1954-07-04  
</lido:earliestDate>
```

- No long text in classifying terms (terms, classification)

Causes:

- Human error
- No format check on data acquisition

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification: MATCH-Pattern (regular expression)

Target state: All fields do match their syntactical specifications.

DATA12 Incompatible data types

Description: A field in the database is specified for a particular non-primitive or primitive data type (e.g., Boolean, integer, float), but the registered value or instance does not meet the specifications of the data type in the data model.

Mainly affected quality feature: syntactic accuracy (if syntax or data model rule is available for a field, all the values should adhere to it)

Other affected quality features:

- semantic accuracy (violating syntax could lead to inaccurate information)
- appropriateness (violated syntax reduces understandability)
- precision (if, e.g., a float is needed but an integer is given)

Impact on data quality: The entries are not machine-understandable and maybe even incomprehensible or ambiguous for data users.

Examples:

- Float value instead of an integer as a measurement value

```
<lido:measurementValue>3.761582e-37</lido:measurementValue>
```

Instead of

```
<lido:measurementValue>3</lido:measurementValue>
```

- String value instead of boolean

Causes:

- Wrong inputs during data collection
- No (automatic) data validation concerning data model specification (during data acquisition)

Root in the data life cycle: Collect

Identification:

- MATCH-Pattern: The registered value does not fulfill the required structure of the data type
- Validation of the data model

Target state: All registered values match the data type's structure associated with its data field.

Terms and Definitions

Data Record: The experts understand a data record as a dataset for an entry that is related in terms of content, such as metadata for a painting or a person. In LIDO, this record is expressed by a parent non-leaf element.

(Data) Field: The experts handle fields in terms of data as the smallest part of a record. We refer to this smallest part as leaf elements. Thus, each record usually consists of several fields. A data field is identified by the field name, the data type, and the value. Examples of fields are gender, date of birth, and postal code.

(Data Model) Field: The experts handle fields in terms of data models as the smallest part of a data model. Thus, we see data model fields as property types of model elements.

Reference: For the experts, a reference is a link to a dataset, record, or element. In the cultural heritage domain, linked data increase quality. This usually involves linking information to other datasets or types to vocabularies.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful for the support we received during this document's work. Therefore, thanks go to everyone who participated in the interviews and the workshop and provided valuable insights, perspectives, and discussions. Your contributions have been essential in making this catalog possible and will help us to extend our work for data quality. We also extend our thanks to all the reviewers who provided us with constructive feedback and suggestions. Your comments helped us refine our arguments and significantly improved the quality of this document. We appreciate the support and encouragement that we have received from everyone.